

CLIMAGEN

ClimaLabs Framework Definition

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Living Labs focusing on Climate-resilient
regeneration and renaturing

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Executive Summary

This 'ClimaLabs Framework Definition' describes the common methodological approach to setting up and scaling up ClimaLabs, including Living Labs, with a focus on climate-resilient regeneration and renaturing in the ClimaGen project. These Living Labs are implemented across the nine ClimaGen participating cities: Belgrade (Serbia), Gdańsk (Poland), Tartu (Estonia), Torino (Italy), Trondheim (Norway), Cluj-Napoca (Romania), Eindhoven (Netherlands), Gernika (Spain) and Thessaloniki (Greece).

Within ClimaGen, Living Labs serve as structured yet flexible platforms for local and regional collaborative governance. They bring together stakeholders across arts, culture and youth, entrepreneurship and financing, and organisational resilience to support long-term planning strategies. By placing co-creation at their core, they empower stakeholders to take an active part in regeneration and renaturing processes, and act as the engagement platform for the development of ClimaGreens in each city. These interventions integrate renaturing measures that address climate change adaptation and mitigation, biodiversity, circularity, health and well-being, social, cultural, and artistic perspectives, and financial and governance structures. ClimaGen Living Labs are built towards the city greening areas and integrate youth entrepreneurship, finance and partnership models, and city dialogues.

Building on this role, this report introduces the general Living Lab approach, outlines its relevance and specific adaptation to the ClimaGen concept, and provides guidance on co-creation processes, governance models and the use of tools and methods based on the Design Thinking process and including their key characteristics. It also offers a framework for setting up Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and monitoring Living Lab activities, financial considerations, and youth engagement, alongside an overview of the ClimaGen cities' current status in establishing their Living Labs.

This deliverable offers key outcomes that form the foundation for the implementation of Living Labs across ClimaGen:

- A shared conceptual and operational framework outlining how ClimaGen Living Labs can be designed, governed, and integrated into local innovation ecosystems.
- Initial guidelines on methods and tools that ClimaGen Living Lab teams can use for Capacity Building, co-creation, stakeholder engagement, and cross-city collaboration.
- A set of common objectives and KPIs to support alignment across cities and strengthen the connection with WP3's monitoring and impact-assessment work.
- A baseline understanding of cities' co-creation activities and current Living Lab maturity across the participating cities.

Together, these elements support a harmonised yet flexible approach that allows each city to adapt its ClimaGen Living Lab to local governance structures, socioeconomic conditions, and

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climate-mitigation and climate-resilience priorities, while facilitating structured cross-city learning, co-creation, and monitoring.

This framework builds on existing principles and best practices of the Living Lab approach to define a common operational model to be used with the ClimaGreen renaturing measures in each ClimaGen city (WP5-WP13). Positioned within WP2, it also establishes connections with WP3 (ClimaImpact) by defining preliminary KPIs and monitoring considerations, and with WP4 (ClimaValue) by providing initial guidance for co-creation and Capacity Building activities.

The deliverable is intended for and developed with all project partners involved in the development and operation of the ClimaGen Living Labs, including public administrations, universities, research centres, NGOs, and other local actors directly contributing to the co-creation, experimentation, monitoring, and upscaling processes within the nine cities. It will support the next phases of the project, including the development of the ClimaGen Impact model Definition (D3.3), ClimaGen Guidance Package (D4.3), ClimaGen Games and methods (D1.9), the operationalisation of Capacity-Building and mentoring activities under WP4, and the application of the ClimaLabs concept and the Living Labs method in all cities (WP5-WP13). More broadly, the framework is relevant for professionals planning, managing, or facilitating local open innovation ecosystems that support climate adaptation and resilience. It is also intended for others who wish to understand and learn from the ClimaGen approaches and methods.

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1. Introduction

ClimaGen brings together nine European cities (Belgrade, Gdańsk, Tartu, Torino, Trondheim, Cluj-Napoca, Eindhoven, Gernika and Thessaloniki) to boost climate resilience, adapt to accelerating climate impacts, and contribute to the shift to low-carbon, inclusive urban systems. The European Green Deal's mission-oriented approach addresses these twin priorities through two of its complementary Missions: the Mission on 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030¹ and the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change². ClimaGen as an innovation action responds to these two Missions to tackle the combined mitigation–adaptation challenge in urban areas. In line with the EU's Just Transition goals³, the cities will carry out greening and renaturing actions that contribute to the Missions. Specifically, the five demonstration cities (Belgrade, Gdańsk, Tartu, Torino, and Trondheim) will implement a 25% increase in new or restored public green spaces, and the four replication cities (Cluj-Napoca, Eindhoven, Gernika and Thessaloniki) aim to experiment with shorter-term co-creative measures. These actions are developed and implemented through city-level Living Labs, referred to as ClimaGen Living Labs and related activities, where ClimaGen partners and local stakeholders work together to transform vulnerable neighbourhoods into resilient, climate-neutral, and regenerated public spaces that improve life for local communities. This work is done under principles of the New European Bauhaus⁴ and a strong co-creation approach.

ClimaGen Living Labs function as place-based, open innovation environments where local authorities, citizens, researchers, civil society, and private actors collaborate to co-create, test, and refine solutions for climate-resilient urban regeneration. Through real-life experimentation and stakeholder engagement, they support the development of inclusive and locally grounded interventions that respond to specific urban challenges while contributing to broader climate mitigation and adaptation objectives.

This Framework Definition (Deliverable 2.1) presents the common methodological approach within which ClimaGen Living Labs operate. It is addressed to ClimaGen Living Lab demonstration and replication cities, while providing a good example to cities not involved in the ClimaGen project and interested in adopting similar approaches. Operating across diverse urban contexts with varying priorities, planning cultures, urban densities and socio-economic conditions, the framework provides a shared reference that ensures coherence across cities while allowing local adaptation and flexibility. D2.1 will be made available via the following [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18965434](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18965434). Any subsequent updates, should they be necessary, will also be accessible through versioning of the same DOI via Zenodo to support traceability and findability.

It is important to underline that D2.1 does not cover the hands-on implementation, monitoring, or evaluation of ClimaLab activities, which will be performed by and at the level of each ClimaGen Living Lab. Nor does it cover aspects related to project-bound impact assessment or technological

¹ *EU Mission: Climate-neutral and Smart Cities*. European Commission, Research and Innovation. (2024). https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities_en

² *EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change*. European Commission, Research and Innovation. (2024). https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/adaptation-climate-change_en

³ *The Just Transition Mechanism: making sure no one is left behind*. European Commission. (2021). https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/finance-and-green-deal/just-transition-mechanism_en

⁴ New European Bauhaus website, https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

development. This ensures a clear boundary between methodological design and operational execution.

Building on established Living Lab literature, the European Network of Living Labs' (ENoLL) 20 years of experience collaborating with Living Labs around the world, and best practices, the framework embeds co-creation as a core principle throughout the Living Lab lifecycle, including co-design, co-development, and co-implementation. It emphasises meaningful stakeholder and citizen involvement as a prerequisite for building trust, strengthening local ownership, and enhancing the long-term sustainability of climate-resilient solutions developed within ClimaGen Living Labs.

ClimaGen Living Labs are expected to be implemented in all participating cities. ENoLL is responsible for a common approach and has led the development of the Living Lab framework, including its key principles, components, definitions, and stakeholders, based on its extensive experience. Both desk research and collaborative work with project partners informed the development of this deliverable. In alignment with the overall project description and the objectives outlined in the Description of Action (DoA), ENoLL conducted desk research to review existing methodological approaches relevant to Living Labs, nature-based solutions (NbS), open innovation ecosystems, co-creation processes, and monitoring structures. This review examined references such as the booklet *Living Lab origins, developments, and future perspectives*⁵, *Urban Living Lab Framework*⁶ developed within UNaLab, the *Living Lab Methodology and Online Handbook*⁷ from REWAISE, and the *Good Practice Guidelines for setting-up and managing Urban Living Labs*⁸ developed by Urbanome. The insights from these sources informed the development of a ClimaGen-specific methodological foundation tailored to the project's climate-resilient regeneration ambitions. In parallel, input from ClimaGen cities was collected through a cities-focused survey, a follow-up online consultation session, and two in-person workshops held during the project study visits in Trondheim and Gernika in 2025.

Figure 1 First stage of the implemented approach for cities' involvement in ClimaLabs

The first workshop in Trondheim served as a starting point for conceptualising what ClimaGen Living Labs are and how the cities envision their role and operation within the project. The second workshop in Gernika provided a platform for cities to exchange experiences, learn from co-creation activities already initiated, and share plans for upcoming Living Lab interventions. Insights gathered through the survey helped map the current status of the ClimaGen Living Lab development, identify challenges and needs, and understand the diversity of local contexts in each

⁵ European Network of Living Labs, Schuurman, D., DeLosRíos-White, M. I., & Desole, M. (2025). *Living Lab origins, developments, and future perspectives*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14764597>

⁶ Ståhlbröst, A., Habibipour, A., Chronéer, D., Vaittinen, I., Zalokar, S., & Mafe, C. (2018). UNaLab ULL framework. Mafe, "UNALAB ULL FRAMEWORK," <https://unalab.eu/en/documents/d21-unalab-ull-framework>

⁷ Bodi, Z., DeLosRíos-White, M. I., & Enriquez, L. (2021). REWAISE Living Lab methodology and online handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12806747>

⁸ ENoLL, AUTH, ISERM, USTUTT, CdM, ADDMA, AU, ENVE.X, AMBIT, IUSS, JSI, CIEMAT, ISCII, RGU (2022) URBANOME Good Practice guidelines for setting up and managing Urban Living Labs. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15781292>

city. The structure of this framework was drafted by ENoLL in close collaboration with project partners NTNU, GIB and SINTEF, and inputs from all other partners linked with the ClimaGen Living Labs and the nine ClimaGen cities.

The framework definition will serve as a living reference throughout the project lifecycle and beyond. Its implementation and refinement will be supported through T2.1 activities and T2.4's City Dialogues coordinated by NTNU, involving cities and their local partners and stakeholders at each project phase. City Dialogues will enable ongoing reflection on needs and priorities, improve their implementation and make sure the work remains aligned with the framework definition. Experiences from the operation of the nine ClimaGen Living Labs, including results and learnings, will be documented in ClimaLabs Experience Reports (D2.1, D2.4, D2.6), aligned with this framework. In addition, further training material and practical support on how to set up and run a Living Lab will be developed under T2.4, and will be based on the principles set out in this deliverable. Other Tasks that will contribute to the implementation of the framework in a later stage are T2.2, for organising youth entrepreneurship programmes in ClimaGen, and T2.3, by co-creating tailored investment and partnership models with each city to support their activities. Beyond WP2, the framework will play a transversal role across the project. It will provide input to WP3 by informing the monitoring and evaluation approach for Living Lab activities in T3.2 and T3.3, and contribute to WP4 and the development of the ClimaGen Guidance Package under T4.2, for methodological coherence across outputs. In this way, the Living Lab framework operates in tandem with other work packages and deliverables, acting as a core element for ClimaGen's climate-resilient regeneration approach.

2. Conceptual & Theoretical Background

2.1 What are Living Labs

Living Labs are open and dynamic ecosystems for innovation, where new ideas are developed and tested in real-life settings. They follow a structured co-creation process that connects research, experimentation, and community engagement, placing citizens and end-users at the core of innovation. This approach not only generates creative solutions but also ensures that outcomes are grounded in real-world needs and contexts.

While the Living Lab concept originally emerged in the field of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), particularly for large-scale digital innovations, it has expanded across many domains. Today, Living Labs operate in diverse areas such as sustainability, healthcare, mobility, agriculture, and urban development, among others. Living Labs are especially effective in tackling the so-called *wicked problems*, which are complex challenges that are hard to define, involve many interdependent factors, and affect multiple stakeholders with differing interests. Issues such as climate change, rapid urbanisation, and social inequality are examples of such problems. The Living Lab approach, with its participatory and adaptive nature, provides a collaborative structure to address these challenges by bringing together varied perspectives and continuously refining solutions as needs evolve.

As defined by ENOLL⁹ Living Labs are:

“user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings”.

Living Labs function as collaborative environments that unite multiple stakeholders, governments, businesses, universities, non-profit organisations, and citizens to encourage shared learning, experimentation, and innovation. Their strength lies in combining diverse perspectives and areas of expertise to guide innovation. By involving users directly in real-world contexts, Living Labs provide an experimentation space for new ideas and solutions, ensuring that outcomes are relevant, adaptable, and effective in practice. End-users should always be at the centre of the process, as active co-creators shaping and improving the products, services, and policies that are being developed. This participatory approach ensures that innovations emerging from Living Labs are relevant and rooted in the real needs of the people and communities they are designed to benefit.

The term Living Lab refers both to the organisational scheme and to the specific projects, tools, and methods applied within that structure. These elements together form the three-layered model, which is further explained in chapter 2.2 The Three-Layered Model of Living Labs.

Living Labs operate as intermediaries among citizens, academia, public authorities, and industry. These four actors in society are known as the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM). An innovation model that is also often looked at for socio-ecological transition is the Quintuple Helix Model, shown in **Figure 2**. It expands the Quadruple Helix by adding the helix (and perspective) of the *natural environments of society*¹⁰. This extended helix model reframes innovation as a process of co-evolution between knowledge, society, economy and nature and ensures that:

- Innovation is aligned with sustainability, rather than causing environmental harm

⁹ European Network of Living Labs, Schuurman, D., DeLosRíos-White, M. I., & Desole, M. (2025). Living Lab origins, developments, and future perspectives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14764597>

¹⁰ Carayannis, E.G., Barth, T.D. & Campbell, D.F. The Quintuple Helix innovation model: global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation. *J Innov Entrep* 1, 2 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1186/2192-5372-1-2>

- Climate change, biodiversity loss and resource depletion are factored into decision-making
- Solutions are designed for long-term resilience, not just short-term economic benefits
- Stakeholders work together in eco-innovation ecosystems, ensuring cross-sector impact

Figure 2 Quintuple helix model, based on the work of Carayannis et al. (2012)

2.2 The Three-Layered Model of Living Labs

There are three layers within which a Living Lab operates: the macro, meso and micro levels¹¹. This model can help clarify the scope and focus of Living Labs, based on the variety of parties involved in the activities and is visualised in **Figure 3**. It is important to keep in mind that a Living Lab to be considered as such must operate at the macro level, of course, through projects (meso) and the activities (micro) they entail.

Macro Level (Living Lab Organisation)

At the macro level, the Living Lab is a sole-standing organisation that has its own stable ecosystem and operates with a long-term vision. It is not only an organisation supported by a project or a series of projects, but it can generate revenue and operate sustainably through its various offerings. There, all relevant actors and stakeholders of the quadruple helix are represented and have an active role within the Living Lab and its activities. In the macro layer, a Living Lab sets goals and objectives with longevity in mind and creates collaborations that are strategic and support this long-term plan.

Meso Level (Living Lab Projects)

The meso level refers to the projects undertaken by Living Labs that aim to support their operations, develop innovations and generate knowledge. Those projects must support the overall objectives and goals of the Living Lab at the macro level and be relevant, adaptable and problem-focused. They are used as a means to achieve the objectives of the organisation as set in the macro level.

¹¹ Schuurman, D. (2015). Bridging the gap between Open and User Innovation: exploring the value of Living Labs as a means to structure user contribution and manage distributed innovation. Ghent University. Faculty of Political and Social Sciences ; Vrije Universiteit Brussel. Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences, Ghent ; Brussels, Belgium.

Micro Level (Living Lab activities and methods)

The micro level entails the activities, research and stakeholder interactions that a Living Lab project is working on. This includes the tools and methodologies that the Living Lab representatives employ to achieve the objectives of each activity. These activities can be workshops, experiments, interviews, surveys, and many other forms of user engagement. Living Labs that have developed specific methodologies can offer these as a service to others, which can support the expansion of a Living Lab's portfolio and broaden its impact.

Overall, at the macro level, there is knowledge transfer between organisations (open innovation). At the meso level, the real-life experimentation and active user involvement happen through a multi-method and multi-stakeholder approach (open and user innovation). At the micro level happens the user involvement and contribution for innovation (user innovation).

Figure 3 The three-layered model of Living Labs, Schuurman, D. (2015)

2.3 When to use a Living Lab

Living Labs are most valuable when tackling complex challenges that require collaborative, real-life experimentation, and involvement of research, policy, and practice. Compared to top-down approaches, Living Labs enable solutions to be co-created and tested in real-life contexts. Without such an approach, interventions risk being technically sound but socially disconnected, poorly adopted, or difficult to scale. By embedding experimentation within everyday life, Living Labs increase the relevance, acceptance, and long-term viability of solutions while reducing implementation risks. This approach supports iterative learning and cross-sector collaboration for a more systemic and adaptive form of innovation. In this context, ClimaGen implements Living Labs in the nine participating cities as a structured mechanism to bridge strategic climate objectives with locally grounded action.

Such complex challenges appear across diverse domains, from climate resilience and sustainable energy to social innovation, emerging technologies, and policy development. The following paragraphs outline the main types of Living Labs based on ENoLL's Booklet¹² and illustrate when each model is most appropriate, depending on the nature of the challenge, the stakeholders

¹² European Network of Living Labs, Schuurman, D., DeLosRíos-White, M. I., & Desole, M. (2025). Living Lab origins, developments, and future perspectives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14764597>

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involved, and the desired outcomes. It is important to mention that the categories below are not strictly defined and might have overlapping characteristics between them.

Living Labs for Grand Societal Challenges

These Living Labs address societal and environmental issues. Their aim is to contribute to long-term sustainability through co-creation and experimentation. Typical examples include Living Labs that address topics such as renewable energy, climate adaptation, public health, water and soil management, resource efficiency and sustainable farming practices. They often bring together public authorities, researchers and communities to test and refine solutions that respond to urgent global and local challenges.

Living Labs for Inclusive Soci(et)al Engagement

These Living Labs focus on promoting social inclusion, equitable economic development, and community resilience. They aim to empower citizens, strengthen local capacities, and address social inequalities through participatory processes. Art, culture and creativity are an important component as they support active participation, dialogue, and raise awareness of social issues. Outcomes may include new policies, participatory governance models, community-driven initiatives, and social entrepreneurship activities for long-term social and economic impact.

Living Labs for Business and Emerging Technology

These Living Labs focus on developing, testing, and scaling digital technologies, platforms and services. They often explore emerging fields such as AI, augmented or virtual environments (e.g. CitiVerse), quantum computing and educational technologies. They are typically led or supported by companies, infrastructure providers or research organisations that use the Living Lab environment to validate technologies and explore new business models. Beyond technology testing, they may also support innovation in sectors such as mobility, automotive, logistics, and digital services, often linked to incubators or technology transfer initiatives.

Campus and University Living Labs

Campus and University Living Labs aim to bridge the gap between academic knowledge and societal impact and strengthen collaboration between universities and external stakeholders. Some University Living Labs focus primarily on student-oriented projects, while others on multi-stakeholder collaborations within and beyond the university's ecosystem. Campus-based Living Labs use the university's physical environment as a testing ground for experiments, making them strongly place-focused. Together, both Living Lab types demonstrate the potential of universities as drivers of societal innovation.

Living Labs for Policies, Governance, and Innovation Ecosystems

These Living Labs are closely connected to the regions and communities where they operate and are often led or enabled by public authorities such as municipalities, regional authorities, or national governments. Their main goal is to enhance cooperation and stimulate innovation across local, regional, and national levels.

A common example within this category is the Urban Living Lab. In comparison with other Living Labs, Urban Living Labs adopt a bottom-up approach that is oriented towards citizen-led

innovation, with them being active contributors. They are usually run or supported by local governments and address a wide range of urban issues from mobility and housing to public services and environmental sustainability, tailored to the specific priorities of each community¹³. Some Urban Living Labs originate as temporary pilot projects that evolve into long-term innovation infrastructures, while others are established to operate at broader regional or national scales.

The ClimaGen Living Labs fall under the category of Urban Living Labs. The next chapter takes a closer look at how the Living Lab concept contributes to the aims and objectives of the ClimaGen project and how the Living Lab key characteristics are reflected in the ClimaGen Living Labs.

¹³ Baccarne, B., Mechant, P., Schuurman, D., Colpaert, P., & De Marez, L. (2014). Urban socio-technical innovations with and by citizens. *INTERDISCIPLINARY STUDIES JOURNAL*, 3(4), 143–156. <https://biblio.ugent.be/publication/4365378>

3. The ClimaGen Living Labs

Along with the project’s description, nine ClimaGen cities will demonstrate how regeneration and renaturing for, by and with vulnerable neighbourhoods can contribute towards climate neutrality and climate resilience¹⁴. This calls for a mission-oriented, interdisciplinary approach that links Nature-based Solutions (NbS) with infrastructure design and city planning. NbS are defined by the European Commission as *“solutions inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience. They bring more, and more diverse, nature and natural features and processes into cities, landscapes and seascapes, through locally adapted, resource-efficient and systemic interventions.”*¹⁵

Such complex efforts need to be anchored in institutional frameworks and supported through collaborative forms of governance and community engagement. The ClimaGen Living Labs are providing some of these structures for the demonstrations and are established in or near vulnerable neighbourhoods or those facing socio-economic challenges. These challenges need to be identified to ultimately clarify the issues that this project will tackle in each area. To do so, and to later test potential solutions, experimentation must take place on the ground, meaning in the real environments where the problem exists. This approach allows for the practical limitations and consequences to be uncovered and understood early on and to be managed. Overall, the ClimaGen Living Lab creates an open-innovation environment to test potential solutions directly in the neighbourhoods. Using the Living Lab approach ensures that actions are grounded in local needs, with practical and inclusive actions, and provides the structure to benefit from shared methods and learnings across cities, regions and countries.

The Living Labs in ClimaGen, referred to as ClimaGen Living Labs, will merge Living Lab principles of ENoLL with core elements of the New European Bauhaus (NEB)¹⁶, the EU Cities Mission and its Climate City Contracts¹⁷, as well as the EU Climate Adaptation Mission¹⁸ and the IPCC’s AR6 report¹⁹. This integration is reflected conceptually and methodologically. From the NEB, ClimaGen Living Labs adopt an emphasis on co-design, inclusiveness, sustainability, and the integration of aesthetic and social dimensions into climate-resilient regeneration. The EU Cities Mission and Climate City Contracts as well as the Climate Adaptation Mission inform alignment with long-term climate neutrality strategies. The IPCC report is integrated to create a coherent identity of the ClimaGen Living Labs

¹⁴ Grant Agreement No. 101139637 – ClimaGen, funded under Horizon Europe by the European Union, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101139637>

¹⁵ European Commission (n.d.). *Nature-based Solutions*. European Commission, Research and Innovation. Retrieved November 18, 2025, from https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/nature-based-solutions_en#email

¹⁶ *New European Bauhaus - About the initiative*. New European Bauhaus. (n.d.). https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/about/about-initiative_en

¹⁷ *EU Mission: Climate-neutral and Smart Cities*. European Commission, Research and Innovation. (2024). https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities_en

¹⁸ *EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change*. European Commission, Research and Innovation. (2024). https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/adaptation-climate-change_en

¹⁹ Lee, Hoesung, et al. (2023) *Synthesis report of the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), Longer report*. IPCC. Technical Report. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/sixth-assessment-report-cycle/>

Based on the project description, the following key principles can be identified for the ClimaGen Living Labs:

- They balance climate mitigation, climate adaptation, (re)greening, biodiversity and nature-based solutions, and co-creation and engagement, for inclusive development
- They draw on cultural traditions and local knowledge, as well as scientific expertise
- They integrate natural, physical, and social infrastructures
- They have a strong focus on equity, climate justice, social justice, inclusion, and just transition.
- They are well embedded within the cities and within the project structures, and they include Youth Engagement, Financial and Partnership Models, and City Dialogues and project and engagement methods.

These key principles abide by the six fundamental building blocks of Living Labs, as described in the coming paragraphs.

3.1 Building blocks of the ClimaGen Living Lab

ClimaGen Living Labs, as all Living Labs, are consistently shaped by six fundamental characteristics that are common to all of them: Co-creation, Orchestration, Multi-stakeholder participation, Active User Involvement, Real Life Setting and Multi-method Approach, as shown in **Figure 4**.

The following paragraphs describe what each of these six blocks entails as described by ENOLL²⁰, and how these characteristics will be covered in each ClimaGen Living Lab. Chapter 4 continues with tools and methods for their concrete implementation.

Figure 4. The six building blocks of a Living Lab by ENOLL⁹

Multi-stakeholder participation

Living Labs embrace an inclusive perspective by involving a wide range of stakeholders, generally represented through the Quadruple Helix Model: public authorities, research institutions,

²⁰ European Network of Living Labs, Schuurman, D., De Los Ríos-White, M. I., & Desole, M. (2025). Living Lab origins, developments, and future perspectives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14764597>

businesses, and citizens or civil society organisations. This diversity of actors strengthens the innovation process by enabling mutual learning, and collaboration.

The ClimaGen project brings together municipalities, universities, SMEs, civil society organisations, financiers, developers, youth, citizen associations, volunteers, artists, and residents in each city to form cross-sector ClimaGen Living Lab ecosystems. Special attention is given to youth involvement as a crucial stakeholder group in all activities. The participatory mapping of stakeholders helps ensure inclusion of underrepresented groups and improve diversity in engagement, as laid out in D1.2 Inclusiveness and Diversity Management Plan.

Some examples of multi-stakeholder involvement in ClimaGen are: linking municipal planners, researchers, and local cultural centres to align climate-neutral strategies with community ambitions (Trondheim); combining municipal actors with art-science institutions and private developers to translate technical NbS into community spaces (Belgrade); integrating local education and entrepreneurship networks to connect youth, academia, and the green economy (Cluj-Napoca).

Real-life setting

Living Labs operate in real-world environments, which means that they conduct co-creation, experimentation and gather feedback in everyday settings.

Each of the nine ClimaGen cities has selected a demonstration area which can be a brownfield industrial site, harbour area, urban park, urban-rural connection, housing neighbourhood facing socio-economic challenges, or similar. These areas are citizens' homes, workplaces or recreation areas through which ClimaGen Living Labs demonstrate how regeneration and renaturing designed for, by and with the local stakeholders can contribute to climate neutrality and resilience. Details have initially been described in D3.1 ClimaGen Impact Pathways, and will be expanded in the upcoming D3.3 ClimaGen Impact Model Definition, and in detail in the first City Reports expected in 2026.

Real-life experimentation is an essential mechanism through which ClimaGen Living Labs translate identified neighbourhood challenges into actionable, co-created solutions. In the context of climate resilience, it allows stakeholders to collaboratively design, prototype, and test NbS under authentic urban conditions, where climate impacts, social dynamics, and spatial constraints intersect. By testing interventions directly in the local environment, ClimaGen Living Labs enable cities to assess how NbS perform in practice, uncover operational barriers, and refine measures iteratively. This strengthens local ownership, supports evidence-based decision-making, and increases technical effectiveness and social acceptance.

Examples of such interventions are community-based gardens and urban farms, wetlands, pocket parks, green corridors, rain gardens, permeable pavements, indigenous tree planting, urban forests, nature-based play areas, restored habitats, green roofs and walls, or rewilding initiatives. Beyond their environmental function, such interventions also generate broader benefits for circularity, public health, cultural identity, and social cohesion.

Through this process, ClimaGen Living Labs become active learning environments where many stakeholders jointly shape climate-resilient futures tailored to each neighbourhood's needs. Chapter 3.4 on ClimaGen Living Lab Stakeholders dives deeper into these types of stakeholders involved in the ClimaGen Living Labs.

Orchestration

A Living Lab functions as an orchestrator by facilitating collaboration, coordinating efforts, and ensuring that the innovation activities align with shared objectives. Locally, orchestration is operationalised through steering groups bringing together public authorities, cultural mediators, and financial partners to guide long-term governance.

Within ClimaGen, Living Labs implement the orchestration role by acting as the central coordination hubs of their local innovation ecosystems. Each ClimaGen Living Lab brings together municipalities, citizens, civil society organisations, businesses, academia and cultural actors, ensuring that these diverse stakeholders are connected and engaged throughout the process. As orchestrators, ClimaGen Living Labs lead the co-creation journey and coordinate activities across planning, experimentation, implementation and monitoring. This includes defining common protocols for data collection and sharing, managing a central data platform to ensure open access for planners and communities and aligning monitoring results with urban greening and climate adaptation policies.

Active user involvement

By actively involving end-users and stakeholders in multiple stages of development, Living Labs ensure that feedback and insights are integrated throughout the innovation process, from ideation to implementation and testing.

In ClimaGen, citizens are the central actors in co-creating and testing NbS. Residents are engaged directly through participatory workshops, artistic interventions, platforms and hands-on experimentation processes tailored to each local context. For example, gamification approaches and youth start-up programmes in Tartu connect students and residents in co-designing prototypes of urban greening; public events like City Picnics and visual art festivals in Gdańsk foster ownership and dialogue around water-related NbS; local gardeners and schools in Torino are involved in renaturing works along the Sangone River; and neighbourhood associations and cooperatives in Gernika test community-driven regeneration ideas.

Multi-method approach

Each Living Lab activity is problem driven, and methods are selected according to the context, desired outcomes and stakeholders involved. As a result, Living Labs utilise a variety of methods and innovation activities, ranging from exploratory to validation approaches, depending on the nature of the problem and the needs of the participants.

Across ClimaGen, Living Labs combine digital, creative, and participatory methods, each of them tailored to the specific local context. Traditional methods such as door-to-door actions, informal talks, and arts-based engagement (visual arts, performances, design workshops) complement high-tech tools to ensure inclusiveness across digital literacy levels.

ClimaLabs Joint Learning Session, *Sense-Making Sessions* and *City Dialogues* provide support and advice for cross-city learning, guidance on financing mechanisms, and adaptation of tools to local context and partners. In parallel, data-driven models assess ecological, economic, and social impacts, grounding creative experimentation in evidence. This methodological diversity allows ClimaGen cities to experiment, learn, and refine solutions while maintaining sensitivity to local culture and social diversity.

Co-creation

Living Labs promote collaborative innovation by involving stakeholders in the design and development of solutions. Innovation is not a linear or closed process but an ecosystem-driven activity built on openness and cross-sector collaboration.

In ClimaGen, co-creation is the core of the innovation cycles, merging artistic, scientific, economic, and civic perspectives. Although co-creation is based on an explorative environment where outcomes cannot be fully predicted, ClimaGen Living Labs provide structured, yet flexible spaces for stakeholders to jointly test NbS and innovative financial models.

Through co-creation processes, ClimaGen Living Labs can:

- Address real needs and vulnerabilities by basing interventions in the real-life experiences of residents, especially in neighbourhoods that are considered socially or environmentally vulnerable.
- Strengthen trust, collaboration and legitimacy of climate actions, sometimes in areas where authorities and communities have limited or fragmented relationships.
- Facilitate knowledge exchange between scientific, technical and experiential expertise.
- Support systemic innovation by linking different government levels and sectors, ensuring alignment between municipal departments, regional strategies, local businesses, youth initiatives, cultural actors, grassroots organisations and citizens
- Enhance long-term sustainability by empowering local actors to maintain and possibly evolve the results post-project.

Co-creation practices allow early discussions on fears, expectations, cultural practices and spatial preferences. This ensures that the NbS implemented responds to the community's priorities without introducing unintended risks, such as safety or accessibility issues. Additionally, and considering the culture and arts priority in ClimaGen, NbS must reflect local identity, heritage and values of the area and its locals. Conflicts, such as land-use concerns, are addressed transparently and early in the process. Lastly, youths, vulnerable and underrepresented residents are given the means to participate meaningfully in shaping their local environment. Through this process, co-creation supports not only the design of NbS, but also social resilience, reinforcing community agency and belonging.

Each ClimaGen Living Lab operates within a unique local ecosystem. This means that no single engagement model fits all cities, but instead, ClimaGen Living Labs must select approaches that best match their context while remaining aligned with the project's co-creation principles. When considering the co-creation strategies, it is important to keep in mind:

- Local political dynamics and decision-making processes within the municipalities
- Political situation on a local and national scale
- Cultural and social characteristics of neighbourhoods
- Existing levels of trust between institutions, local authorities and communities
- Stakeholder diversity in interventions, power dynamics and representation gaps
- Past experiences with participation, consultation or public engagement, and the learnings and outcomes
- Physical characteristics of the area of intervention
- Local priorities linked to climate adaptation

Examples from ClimaGen include the organisation of co-design sessions with foundations and residents to determine tree species, street furniture, and festival formats in Torino; the co-development of public space prototypes blending architecture, art, and ecology in Gdańsk; the

integrations of citizen science and university collaboration in Trondheim; the development of a communication and awareness plan ensuring every project phase is participatory, with local associations and cooperatives embedded in decision-making in Gernika. More details on the co-creation principles in a ClimaGen Living Lab are explained in Chapter 4 on Co-creation & Methods.

Beyond communities, Living Lab co-creation requires the involvement of actors from the broader innovation ecosystem, including public authorities, businesses, academia, and civil society organisations. However, multi-stakeholder collaboration brings its own set of challenges. Stakeholders often operate under different mandates, priorities and timeframes, which can lead to conflicting agendas or difficulties in finding shared objectives. Limited time, organisational capacity, or lack of internal incentives may reduce stakeholders' willingness to participate consistently. Power imbalances, such as institutional actors dominating discussions, can also restrict the influence of smaller organisations or community representatives. Furthermore, some stakeholders may be unfamiliar with co-creation approaches or may perceive them as peripheral to their strategic goals, resulting in disengagement or only nominal participation. These challenges highlight the importance of careful stakeholder alignment and trust-building to ensure meaningful collaboration within Living Labs.

3.2 ClimaGen Living Lab Values

The ClimaGen Living Labs share a set of values that guide how cities, stakeholders, and communities collaborate to co-create their neighbourhoods. These values represent shared ambitions that underpin the ClimaGen approach, rather than guaranteed outcomes. While each city operates within its own context and constraints, all ClimaGen Living Labs are working toward these common foundations.

This chapter describes these fundamental environmental, cultural, economic, social and innovation-oriented values as perceived through the ClimaGen Living Lab approach. The list of values was co-created with the participating cities based on their so far experiences and impressions of the operation of their ClimaGen Living Labs, collected through an online survey launched and completed in October 2026.

These values are operationalised through the Living Lab methodology itself, by supporting structured co-creation processes, transparent governance models, iterative experimentation, stakeholder engagement and monitoring activities supported by the project partners. Their realisation depends on continuous reflection, adaptive management and collaboration across work packages. In this way, the values function both as guiding principles and as reference points for assessing progress over time. Based on this shared foundation, each city will further refine and contextualise these values locally throughout the project lifecycle.

Figure 5. ClimaGen Living Labs values

Environmental value

A ClimaGen Living Lab implements practical solutions that improve urban resilience, ecosystem health and the well-being of residents. Interventions such as softening the heat island effect in summer, riverbank reinforcement, and planting diverse varieties of greenery for climate resilience and biodiversity, support climate-adaptive, nature-based, and socially beneficial urban transformation. The ClimaGen Living Lab strengthens ecological functions and ensures that these benefits persist over time.

Cultural value

A ClimaGen Living Lab seeks to create cultural value by strengthening community cohesion and enriching the cultural life of the selected areas. Where local capacities and contexts allow, a Living Lab aims to activate cultural capital through youth engagement, artistic practices, and the integration of culture with small-scale economic activities.

Economic value

Urban greening and renaturing interventions can stimulate local economies by increasing the attractiveness of neighbourhoods, supporting local businesses, and drawing visitors to regenerated areas. At the same time, many benefits materialise as avoided costs, such as reduced pressure on public health systems, improved insurability of physical assets, increased resilience of urban infrastructure, and lower long-term maintenance costs compared to conventional grey infrastructure. By applying socially inclusive and climate-neutral urban planning approaches, and actively involving vulnerable communities, ClimaGen Living Labs aims to contribute to a fair transition towards a more sustainable and inclusive local economy.

Improved innovation

ClimaGen Living Labs with the support of the project partners foster a bottom-up approach, where local actors, researchers, and communities co-design innovative solutions that respond directly to

real needs. It enables the development and testing of NbS in the chosen areas while promoting collaboration between cities and with other projects and initiatives to share insights and best practices for innovation. By involving young people in co-creating nature-based solutions, the ClimaGen Living Lab builds future innovation skills and a sense of ownership. Long-term monitoring of the changes and their effects also provides useful knowledge to support sustainable urban and ecological transitions.

Validity and reliability

Combining on-the-ground research, direct interaction with end users, and tailored methodologies allows the project outcomes to closely meet requirements and needs of stakeholders involved. A ClimaGen Living Lab strives for accurate and reliable results through a clear and open process that involves stakeholders through co-creation methodologies from the early stage. Evaluation is planned and carried out with guidance and support from project partners, ensuring it aligns with the project's goals. Regular reviews and joint decision-making also strengthen the trustworthiness of the results. By using research as a tool for social change, the ClimaGen Living Lab approach ensures that results are both evidence-based and socially meaningful.

Social value

A ClimaGen Living Lab places people and communities at the heart of climate adaptation. By involving the community in the development and planning activities, the area transformation is more likely to benefit the variety of end-users, inhabitants or the area for which these solutions were developed. Promoting green and cultural activities helps to rebrand areas, enhancing their image and social cohesion. A ClimaGen Living Lab strengthens community and business self-organisation, empowering local actors to take ownership of long-term change. It also serves as a channel of communication between citizens, researchers, and decision-makers, fostering transparency and collaboration. Through active community building and engagement, the ClimaGen Living Lab nurtures trust, inclusion, and shared responsibility, ensuring that the benefits of transformation are tangible, equitable, and lasting.

Enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities

By combining multiple methods tailored to each city, area, and societal needs, ClimaGen Living Labs facilitate collaboration among a wide range of stakeholders from the beginning. This engagement allows for dialogue and learning about each other's needs and limitations, which increases transparency and trust throughout the project. Through co-creation and quadruple helix collaboration, bringing together public authorities, academia, businesses, and citizens, the ClimaGen Living Lab becomes a living platform for joint innovation and problem-solving. It encourages a push to cooperate with other local projects, creating synergies and amplifying collective impact. Moreover, it provides an opportunity to initiate multi-departmental cooperation within the city, improving coordination and resource efficiency. By promoting better alignment of goals, methods, and interests, the ClimaGen Living Lab strengthens networks that drive coherent, inclusive, and sustainable transformation.

Safe environment for Research & Development

A ClimaGen Living Lab provides a safe environment for research and development by enabling low-risk, iterative experimentation that can be scaled up. It supports small, scalable pilot projects, offering a tested pathway from ideation and prototyping to wider implementation. The project's timeframe allows learning from failure and steady improvement, while multilevel, step-by-step

implementation lets teams adjust strategies progressively and align interventions across scales. Together, these elements create a space for innovation where strong, adaptable solutions can emerge.

Increased skills and capabilities

A ClimaGen Living Lab strengthens skills and capabilities across institutions and communities by creating hands-on learning opportunities and promoting collaboration. Its greatest value lies in how the local community learns to function as a cohesive and proactive group, gaining confidence and capacity to shape its own environment. Through the ClimaGen Living Lab, city officials and technical staff are also supported on NbS and community-building, helping them learn how to integrate co-design into everyday planning and implementation. Through ClimaGen Living Labs, different sectors are encouraged to work together to map shared challenges and learn from one another. By showing how municipalities can effectively use inhabitants' knowledge, the ClimaGen Living Lab makes co-creation a natural practice. Through these processes, it nurtures participatory decision-making and builds long-term competence, turning collaboration into an embedded skill across the local ecosystem.

While each ClimaGen Living Lab is shaped by its local context, challenges, and community dynamics, these shared values provide a common reference for action and decision-making. Their degree of realisation may vary across cities and over time. However, they serve as guiding commitments that ensure coherence, accountability, and a shared direction towards equitable and climate-resilient urban transformation.

3.3 Governance models

A governance model is the structure through which a Living Lab is managed and directed. It encompasses the processes, policies, procedures, roles, responsibilities and decision-making mechanisms that guide the Living Lab's activities from a strategic and an operational perspective. In **Figure 6** you can see the key functions of a governance model.

As Living Labs are different based on the host organisation, activities, focus and goals, governance models vary between each Living Lab. A clear and well-structured governance model and the processes in place to enforce it are an innovative tool on their own that supports the sustainability of the Living Lab in the long run. However, it is not straightforward how to adapt experiences from others; good analyses of the characteristics of the Living Lab are essential to set up a smart governance structure.

Figure 6 Key functions of a governance model

To ensure the participatory inclusion of all relevant stakeholders, each ClimaGen Living Lab should set in place a clear and transparent governance structure. Such a structure will support defining the roles and responsibilities within the Living Lab, and open and continuous communication among stakeholders. It can also support the Living Lab to act in accordance with ethics, integrity and a responsible code of conduct, and in gaining insights on how to handle societal challenges. This is also a starting point to indicate how and in what aspects the Living Lab should improve.

Governance models must remain flexible and adaptive to context and time. As the ClimaGen Living Lab matures, stakeholder influence, priorities and available resources will evolve, and governance mechanisms should reflect these changes. It is not uncommon for Living Labs that begin, for example, under a municipal or public authority to later transition into independent associations or multi-stakeholder cooperatives to allow the broader engagement of citizens, academia and industry sectors. Such adaptability ensures continuity and shared ownership, while maintaining legitimacy and responsiveness to community and environmental needs.

A robust governance structure supports both the sustainability and viability of the Living Lab by:

- Clarifying stakeholder roles and responsibilities
- Facilitating internal and external communication
- Strengthening decision-making processes
- Upholding ethical standards and integrity
- Laying the foundation for long-term strategic development

Through these principles, ClimaGen Living Labs can effectively address complex societal challenges while promoting trust, inclusiveness and accountability.

The following paragraphs describe a 2-step approach for defining the governance model for a ClimaGen Living Lab.

3.3.1 Host Organisations and Institutional Set-Up

Before defining the governance model, it is essential to identify the host organisation that is best suited to the Living Lab's context and long-term ambitions. The host organisation acts as the central coordinating entity responsible for orchestrating activities, providing essential infrastructure and resources, and offering leadership throughout both the establishment and

operational phases of the Living Lab. Importantly, it should also serve as a neutral party that fosters trust and collaboration among the diverse stakeholders.

Selecting the right host organisation is a strategic decision that significantly influences the Living Lab's success and sustainability. The host must be capable of coordinating activities, enabling innovation from the ground up, and supporting collaboration across all stakeholder groups, including civil society, private actors, city departments, and research institutions. A strong host will not only drive initiatives forward but also actively embody and champion the Living Lab's mission and vision.

To fulfil this role effectively, the host organisation should possess some key characteristics and capacities. It should have a clear commitment to open innovation and problem-solving, as well as expertise in communication, collaboration, and knowledge exchange. Operational competence is equally important: the host must be able to manage physical spaces, equipment, and financial resources efficiently. Given the Living Lab's strong emphasis on community engagement, the host should also be well-connected to local civil society and capable of building and maintaining trusted relationships. Finally, the host must be adaptive: able to respond to emerging needs, adjust to changing circumstances, and support the iterative nature of Living Lab activities.

The choice of host will shape the Living Lab's legal structure, funding approach, operational autonomy, and overall positioning within the local ecosystem. Therefore, the host organisation must align with the Living Lab's value proposition, stakeholder landscape, and long-term vision.

Potential host organisations for a Living Lab include:

- Private companies
- Public or municipal authorities
- Regional structures
- Research centres or university departments
- Mutualistic or cooperative organisations
- Clusters or partnerships of organisations
- Non-profit or community-based entities

In ClimaGen, the identification of host organisations has followed a context-driven approach. In most cases, the municipality acts as the formal host or lead coordinator, given its mandate over urban planning and public spaces interventions. In other cities, however, operational coordination is shared with universities, research centres, or local organisations that bring expertise in co-creation and community engagement. During the first project year, cities tried to clarify institutional responsibilities, defined internal coordination structures, and initiated discussions on long-term positioning beyond the project lifetime. In cases where the host structure is still evolving, further adjustments are planned to ensure stronger community anchoring and clearer operational roles in the coming months.

3.3.2 Defining a Governance Model

Once the host organisation is identified, the next step is to establish a governance model that provides clarity, stability, and transparency for all Living Lab activities. A well-designed governance model ensures that the Living Lab operates efficiently, fosters trust among stakeholders, and supports long-term collaboration. To shape this model, several guiding questions can help initiate reflection and co-creation among the involved actors.

A first consideration is identifying *who* the core participants are. Understanding which stakeholders will contribute to the Living Lab, and in what roles, creates the foundation for an inclusive and

functional structure. Equally important is determining *how* these actors will contribute, whether financially or through in-kind resources. This includes defining the budget needed for setup and operations, and agreeing on how specific activities, experiments, or projects will be financed.

Decision-making processes also require careful attention. The governance model should specify how Living Lab activities are initiated, who is responsible for handling different phases of the work, and which actors are authorised to engage partners, manage resources, or sign agreements. In addition to formal procedures, the model should outline how day-to-day operations are coordinated and how longer-term strategies and implementation plans are developed.

Communication constitutes another essential pillar of governance. Clear, accessible, and tailored communication channels should be established for each stakeholder group, ensuring that all actors, from community members to private partners, can engage meaningfully and remain informed throughout the process.

Finally, the governance model should articulate the value proposition for each participant. Benefits may come in many forms: social impact, financial returns, prototypes, services, intellectual property, or enhanced local resilience, and understanding these expectations helps sustain long-term involvement. Together, these considerations help define both the structural components of governance (who is involved and in what capacity) and the mechanisms that enable collaboration, accountability, and shared ownership of the Living Lab's outcomes.

In practice, ClimaGen cities have begun shaping their governance models through stakeholder mapping exercises, meetings and co-creation workshops. Core participant groups have been identified in all nine cities, although their level of formalisation differs, depending on local maturity and institutional capacity. Over the next project phase and through hands-on workshops led through T2.1, governance arrangements will be further clarified, particularly regarding roles, engagement mechanisms and financing models, ensuring alignment with the evolving needs of each Living Lab and with the monitoring requirements of WP3.

3.4. ClimaGen Living Lab Stakeholders

ClimaGen Living Labs engage a broad range of stakeholders who are either directly involved in, affected by, or capable of influencing regeneration and renaturing actions.

Rather than applying a fixed categorisation model, each Living Lab conducts a context-specific stakeholder mapping process during its initial phase. This includes:

- Identifying actors with decision-making authority, local knowledge, or implementation capacity
- Analysing levels of interest, influence, and potential contribution
- Recognising vulnerable or underrepresented groups who should be meaningfully included
- Clarifying roles in co-design, testing, financing, or long-term maintenance

Stakeholder mapping is typically carried out through desk research, bilateral meetings, snowball identification methods, and early co-creation workshops. Several cities complement this with power-interest matrices or ecosystem mapping exercises to understand relationships and potential conflicts.

Engagement formats vary depending on stakeholder type and role. Municipal departments and regional authorities are often involved through formal coordination meetings and policy alignment workshops. Local communities participate through participatory design sessions, neighbourhood dialogues, artistic interventions, and hands-on experimentation. Businesses and financial actors engage in targeted roundtables, pilot co-development processes, and financing discussions, particularly in relation to market uptake and long-term sustainability of NbS interventions.

It is useful to distinguish between stakeholders, users, and customers:

- Stakeholders: are individuals or entities who have a stake in the activities, outcomes or impacts of the ClimaGen Living Lab. They may contribute resources, expertise, or support to the Living Lab and may be affected by its initiatives and decisions.
- Users: are individuals or groups who directly interact with the products, services or interventions developed and tested within the ClimaGen Living Lab. Their input, feedback, experiences and needs are critical for informing the design, implementation, and evaluation of Living Lab initiatives. They are the end-users of the generated solutions.
- Customers: are individuals who would potentially pay for the generated solutions or are willing to invest in them

Many times, these categories overlap. This is the case in ClimaGen Living Labs, where the local community is the final user of the developed NbS and an active contributor in all stages of problem-solving through a participatory approach. In addition, those willing to finance or in other way financially enable the developed solutions, i.e. ClimaGreens are both customers and key stakeholders of the ClimaLabs, as market-ready solutions cannot be developed without their involvement.

As mentioned, ClimaGen Living Labs should apply a collaborative approach that involves all actors of the quintuple helix. Although the intermediaries involved in the ClimaGen Living Labs differ per city, general groups can be identified as shown in **Table 1**.

Public sector	<p>City councils and municipal authorities</p> <p>Regional and national authorities</p> <p>Urban planning and environmental departments</p> <p>Policy makers and regulators</p> <p>European and national policy initiatives (EU Missions, New European Bauhaus, etc.)</p> <p>Municipal utilities and public development agencies</p> <p>Public financiers (EIB, EBRD, EU Cohesion Fund, foundations, grant makers, etc.)</p>
Academia	<p>Universities and research institutions</p> <p>R&D clusters and innovation ecosystems</p> <p>Students (involved in ideation and co-creation workshops)</p> <p>Research-driven Living Labs and scientific networks</p>
Industry	<p>Start-ups and SMEs</p> <p>Social enterprises</p> <p>Business incubators and accelerators</p> <p>Private investors and financial experts</p> <p>Cultural and creative industries (arts, design, media)</p> <p>Infrastructure developers and entrepreneurs</p> <p>Banks and private sector finance actors</p>
Civil society	<p>Local communities and neighbourhood associations</p> <p>Citizens and inhabitants of the target areas</p> <p>Youth groups and schools (Youth Entrepreneurship Programme)</p> <p>NGOs and civil society initiatives for ecology and regeneration</p> <p>Cultural and artistic associations</p> <p>Vulnerable and underrepresented groups</p> <p>Volunteers and citizen-science participants</p>
Natural environment	<p>Urban green and blue infrastructures</p> <p>Ecosystems and biodiversity networks</p> <p>Nature-based solutions (NbS) projects and practitioners</p> <p>Environmental NGOs and conservation organisations</p> <p>Natural heritage and landscape stakeholders</p>

Table 1 Stakeholders identified to be involved in ClimaGen Living Labs

3.4.1 Types of Stakeholder Contribution

A ClimaGen Living Lab relies on contributions from its stakeholders, each of which plays an important role in shaping how the Living Lab operates and evolves. These contributions are not limited to financial resources, but they include the time, expertise, infrastructure, technologies, networks, and community insights that enable real-life experimentation and long-term climate resilience work in the neighbourhoods. Contributions are the operational backbone of the Living Lab and therefore constitute an essential element of its governance model.

It is important to distinguish between stakeholder contribution and stakeholder value, as the two are often linked but serve different purposes. Stakeholder contribution refers to the tangible and intangible inputs that actors bring into the Living Lab. These may include financial resources, personnel time, access to facilities or data, technology, methodological expertise, networks, or community knowledge. Such contributions have an immediate influence on how the Living Lab is coordinated, governed, and implemented.

Stakeholder value, by contrast, concerns what stakeholders gain from participating in the Living Lab. This might involve social impact, improved services, new prototypes or innovations, strengthened community relations, scientific outputs, or new business opportunities. Stakeholder value is therefore tied to value creation and reflects the long-term benefits and impact generated through the Living Lab's activities and governance processes. Both contribution and value play complementary roles. Together, they shape strategic decisions, help maintain balanced participation, and support the long-term sustainability of the Living Lab.

Different types of contributions serve different functions within the Living Lab:

Financial contributions ensure that operations can be maintained, including coordination tasks, community engagement activities, and the testing of solutions. They allow Living Labs to provide continuity, respond to emerging needs, and carry out experimentation without being fully dependent on external project funding.

In-kind contributions such as physical spaces, equipment, infrastructure access, or logistical support reduce operational barriers and enable cities to test climate-resilience measures directly in the environments where challenges occur. These contributions often come from public administrations, universities, NGOs, or local community organisations.

Technological contributions support the monitoring, implementation, and assessment of nature-based solutions. They include tools for climate modelling, sensing, visualisation, or data collection. In ClimaGen, technological contributions are particularly relevant to support evidence-based planning, measure impacts, and inform decision-making during experimentation.

Human resources, including municipal staff, community volunteers, technical specialists, or researchers, enable the Living Lab to carry out facilitation, fieldwork, design activities, and evaluation tasks. These contributions also help ensure continuity and embeddedness in the local context, both of which are crucial for building trust and maintaining participation.

Knowledge contributions bring scientific, practical, and local experiential expertise into the Living Lab. These contributions help articulate challenges, improve solution quality, and ensure that interventions are both technically robust and socially meaningful. In ClimaGen, where co-creation and climate resilience are central, knowledge exchange across stakeholder groups is essential for the Living Lab to operate as an inclusive innovation process.

Recognising and documenting these contributions helps clarify expectations, strengthen collaboration, and build a governance model that is transparent and resilient. While each city will develop its own structure based on its context, acknowledging early on and throughout operations

the available contributions is essential. **Table 2** provides an overview of the main contribution types and examples of what each stakeholder group may bring into a ClimaGen Living Lab.

Type of Contribution	Examples
Financial	Public funding, private investments, corporate sponsorship
In-kind	Access to facilities, equipment, digital tools
Technological	Platforms, sensors, or software provided by industry partners
Human resources	Volunteers, interns, research assistants, facilitators
Knowledge	Research data, user insights, training materials

Table 2 Common types of contributions for Living Labs

Understanding stakeholder contributions also highlights an essential aspect of Living Lab sustainability: financial resources. While many stakeholders provide in-kind support, access to stable funding remains critical for maintaining core operations, supporting experimentation, and ensuring continuity beyond individual projects. This brings us to one of the most persistent challenges reported by Living Labs across Europe: their financial model, further analysed in the following chapter.

3.3 Financing a ClimaGen Living Lab

Funding, or the lack thereof, is a major concern for most Living Labs, both in their inception and as they evolve. Specifically in ClimaGen, cities are expected to co-create financial models to support their renaturing measures for ClimaGreens. Across Europe, the primary sources of funding remain public grants and subsidy programmes (from local or regional authorities) or project-based funding (local, regional, national or European levels)²¹, even though Living Labs are increasingly expected to respond to private market needs. However, these subsidies often do not provide the long-term stability required to sustain Living Lab operations.

A well-defined business model aims to create and capture value from the implemented activities, allowing the Living Lab to fund itself sustainably. Developing such an economically viable model requires aligning the internal processes of the Living Lab with the needs of its external stakeholders so that revenues are generated²².

Funding models must also be dynamic and adaptable: as Living Labs grow, their funding structures evolve. Mature Living Labs tend to diversify their income streams, moving towards self-sustaining models that balance public support and private partnerships. Given the task of ClimaGen to finance the greening The following sections outline how ClimaGen Living Labs can design sustainable funding pathways, considering different maturity phases and income mechanisms.

Funding needs and opportunities change as Living Labs progress through different stages of maturity. At early stages, activities depend heavily on public or institutional support, while later

²¹ Fasshauer, I. (2020, September). Open Innovation Business Models: the example of living labs in France. In *Open Digital Living Lab Days, European Network of Living Labs*.

²² Katzy, B. (2012). Designing viable business models for living labs. *Technology innovation management review*, 2(9).

phases enable revenue generation and self-sustainability. **Table 3** summarises typical funding resources and priorities per phase.

Maturity Phase	Main Focus	Typical Funding Sources
Ideation	Building vision, mobilising stakeholders	Seed grants, local authority support, university partnerships, in-kind contributions
Set-up	Establishing governance, early pilots	Public grants (local/national/EU), foundations, philanthropy, municipal co-funding
Operational	Delivering services, proving value	Service contracts, membership fees, R&I collaborations
Scaling	Diversifying impact, expanding network	Mixed funding, sponsorships, IP revenues, consulting services, strategic partnerships

Table 3 Typical Funding Sources per Maturity Phase Adapted from ENOLL's Virtual Learning Lab 2025

Beyond these stages, Living Labs often combine different sources to maintain flexibility and ensure continuity over time. Each financing model carries distinct advantages and challenges, and the ideal approach depends on the Living Lab's goals, maturity stage and partnerships in place and available. Below are some of the funding sources that ClimaGen Living Labs can seek when developing their governance strategy, and in other stages of setting up and operating a Living Lab.

Grants are non-repayable funds that support Living Lab activities and growth. They are ideal for launching, testing or scaling ideas without diverting resources from other activities.

- Public grants stem from governmental agencies at the local (e.g. city innovation funds), national (e.g. research agencies) or international levels (e.g. Horizon Europe, GIZ).
- Philanthropic grants come from foundations or charities aligned with specific missions such as environmental sustainability or social innovation.

Living Labs should ensure that they are applying for grants that align with their vision, strengths and capacity, supporting their setting-up and scaling-up without diverging significantly from their focus and objectives.

Many Living Labs generate income by offering services based on their expertise and available infrastructure. These services can support customers and/or partners in their innovation processes, and they vary from one Living Lab to the other. They might be:

- Designing and facilitating co-creation sessions through methods and tools
- Conducting research into user insights and testing concepts in real-life environments
- Recruiting and managing user panels for testing and performing impact assessments
- Testing and validating products, services or policies in real-life contexts

Such services should build on existing strengths, and Living Labs should expand their service portfolio gradually as their capabilities grow.

Some Living Labs charge membership or subscription fees to organisations that benefit from their services or operation. This income stream can support the long-term funding of the Living Lab while reinforcing stakeholder engagement. Subscribers or members, such as SMEs, start-ups, local authorities, NGOs, universities, corporates and other ecosystem actors, gain access to user panels, testing facilities, co-creation spaces, events and innovation processes, as well as visibility and participation in strategic discussions.

Membership schemes can reinforce the Living Lab’s role as a local connector and innovation hub, provided they are managed transparently and inclusively.

Sponsorships allow companies to support Living Labs in exchange for visibility, early access to insights, users and processes or strategic collaboration. Sponsors might contribute to technologies that are showcased in a Living Lab, events, equipment, infrastructure, data platforms, and strategic innovation projects. To maintain credibility, Living Labs should define clear sponsorship tiers or packages, communicate transparently, and distinguish between partners and funders.

Strong sponsorships rely on the Living Lab being seen as a gateway to real users, trusted data and societal impact by potential sponsors. For this, it is important to focus on clearly defining and promoting the Living Lab objectives and brand since the early stages of creation.

Some Living Labs act as incubators for startups or manage innovation outputs such as data and intellectual property (IP). This model leverages a Living Lab’s role in enabling, testing and validating new ideas, and possible streams include:

- participation fees or service contracts
- shared equity or success-based agreements
- licensing fees for methods or results
- subscription access to datasets
- IP co-ownership

IP agreements should be established transparently and early, especially due to the collaborative and co-creative nature of Living Labs.

Strategic partnerships provide financial and in-kind support, helping sustain Living Labs over time.

- Universities and research centres offer access to facilities, students and expertise.
- NGOs can channel donor funds and co-design social innovation projects.
- Municipalities and regional authorities can provide co-funding, policy support and access to public infrastructure for testing or co-creation.

Partnerships should be based on mutual value creation and not only on securing funding, as they can strengthen (or undermine) the legitimacy, capacity and long-term impact of the Living Lab.

Both public and private funding sources play crucial roles in the sustainability of Living Labs. Understanding their differences helps identify strategies that combine stability with innovation and flexibility. **Table 4** offers an overview of who might be a possible funding source for Living Lab.

	Typical Actors	Example Mechanisms	Benefits for the Living Lab	Risks/Considerations
Private Sector	Companies, corporates, investors, foundations	Sponsorships, service contracts, memberships, innovation partnerships	Market orientation, agility, access to industry networks	Risk of mission drift, dependence on commercial interests
Public Sector	Municipalities, regional/national authorities, EU institutions	Companies, corporates, investors, foundations	Stability, legitimacy, alignment with policy priorities	Bureaucracy, limited flexibility, short-term cycles

Table 4 Overview of Public and Private Funding Sources for Living Labs

Sustaining a Living Lab requires ongoing strategy, adaptability and integrity. ClimaGen Living Labs are encouraged to follow these guiding principles:

- Blend grants and revenue: grants help launch and experiment, while revenue from constant sources, such as services and membership, support continuity.
- Evolve: start with simple models and as the Living Lab matures, expand its income streams and test new models of offerings and funding.
- Align funding and purpose: not every opportunity will fit the Living Lab's mission and objectives. Be selective and choose partners and funding streams that align with the Living Lab's goals and values.
- Maintain transparency: implement clear governance for financial decision-making and stakeholder communication.
- Reinvest strategically: use part of the generated income to build reserves and secure future operations.

4. Co-creation in ClimaGen Living Labs

As mentioned in Chapter 3, co-creation is a key principle in open innovation, and a practical mechanism within the ClimaGen context for designing, testing and legitimising regeneration and renaturing interventions in vulnerable urban areas. Within ClimaGen Living Labs, citizens, researchers, policymakers and businesses are all considered active contributors with valuable experiential, scientific, organisational or contextual knowledge. Although the specific methodologies may vary, Living Lab co-creation is grounded in the principles shown in **Figure 7**. In ClimaGen, co-creation follows an iterative process embedded in each Living Lab’s local action cycle which typically include phases such as exploration, co-design, co-implementation, testing, evaluation and scaling.

Figure 7 Key principles of co-creation in ClimaGen Living Labs

For ClimaGen Living Labs to effectively monitor satisfaction, inclusiveness and perceived legitimacy of the activities over time, it is strongly advised to document an initial baseline. This baseline should capture existing perceptions, expectations and motivations of participants, local needs and challenges as well as the levels of trust in the process. It is also important to capture the willingness of people to engage and identify barriers that can possibly prevent participation or create inequities in the course of the co-creation activities. This baseline serves as the foundation for evaluating the evolution of community involvement and for understanding the broader social impact and value created through the Living Lab activities. While Living Labs offer powerful frameworks for collaborative innovation, co-creation in practice may face challenges. Engaging communities in co-creation processes is essential for Living Labs, yet it often presents a series of practical and social challenges. Many community members may have limited awareness of the

Living Lab's purpose or may not immediately recognise the relevance of the activities to their daily lives. Social vulnerability, language barriers¹³, and low levels of trust in public authorities¹⁴ can further hinder participation, particularly in areas facing environmental, economic or social pressures. Additionally, residents may experience participation fatigue¹⁵, especially if they have been involved in previous initiatives that did not lead to visible change. These factors can limit the diversity and representativeness of community voices, making it harder for Living Labs to capture local priorities, establish legitimacy, and build long-term relationships of trust¹⁶.

4.3 The Design Thinking Process

Design Thinking is an established problem-solving process that has existed for decades but only became popular after an article was published in Harvard Business Review in 2008¹⁸. It is particularly suitable for tackling complex, ambiguous and non-linear problems, which are conditions that are typical in Living Lab environments working on urban, social, environmental or technological challenges. Because Living Labs operate across diverse themes, with various user groups and contextual conditions, design thinking offers a structured yet flexible approach for generating solutions that are innovative and grounded in real needs. It supports creativity, systems-thinking and user-centredness, making it highly compatible with the Living Lab model.

Design Thinking consists of five stages (**Figure 8**) through which the solution to the problems becomes clear. These stages guide the methodology users through cycles of divergent (expanding perspectives, exploring possibilities) and convergent (narrowing down, refining) thinking. Through this oscillation, problem and solution spaces become progressively clearer. The methodology described in this sub-chapter is adapted from the Institute of Design at Stanford, Bootcamp bootleg²³.

²³ Doorley, S., Holcomb, S., Klebahn, P., Segovia, K., & Utley, J. (2018). *Design thinking bootleg: An introductory set of tools and methods for approaching a new project.* Stanford d.school. <https://dschool.stanford.edu/resources/the-bootcamp-bootleg>

Figure 8 The five stages of the Design Thinking methodology

4.3.1. Empathise (Diverge)

The process begins with understanding the people affected by the problem, building empathy for them and realising what is important for them, and how. This involves observing people, exploring what individuals do and how they interact with their environments, and engaging directly with them. This process can help to uncover needs, emotions, constraints and aspirations. The aim is not simply to gather information but to build empathy and question initial assumptions. This stage broadens the team’s understanding and ensures that later decisions are rooted in real user experiences and not the team’s own theories.

4.3.2. Define (Converge)

In this stage, insights from the Empathise phase are synthesised into a clearly articulated problem statement or point of view. This involves identifying patterns across user experiences, defining key needs and framing the challenge in a way that can guide ideation. The outcome of this phase should also be used as a reference to revisit and reformulate in later stages as learning evolves. This is a stage of converging, as it narrows a wide field of insights into a focused design challenge.

4.3.3. Ideate (Diverge)

The Ideation stage encourages creativity and exploration. The team focuses on generating a wide variety of ideas, whether they seem conventional, unconventional or even unrealistic, without prematurely selecting favourites. Examples of ideation techniques include brainstorming, mind mapping and sketching²⁰, aiming to open the solution range to alternative perspectives. This stage enables the team to move beyond the obvious or habitual solutions, giving space for creative and innovative possibilities to be tested and refined.

4.3.4. Prototype (Converge)

Prototyping aims to turn ideas into a tangible form so that they can be explored, evaluated and discussed. This stage, along with the testing phase, is a process of converging, as its goal is to find the best possible solution at the end of the process. Prototyping is an iterative process that can

take many forms, including sketches, storyboards, mock-ups, models, role-play scripts, interactive maps or temporary physical setups. Early prototypes should be quick and rough to allow fast learning and frequent iteration. Prototyping is also a powerful tool for aligning stakeholders, uncovering disagreements, validating assumptions, and giving shape to abstract concepts. At this stage, involving relevant stakeholders, including representatives from across the quadruple (or quintuple) helix, helps ensure the solution is informed by diverse expertise and perspectives.

4.3.4. Test (Converge and Iterate)

Testing exposes prototypes to users and other stakeholders and gathers insights on how well the proposed solution meets the defined needs. It helps the team understand the usability of the solution, its acceptance, relevance and unintended effects. Testing is not a final step, but an opportunity to visit previous stages of the process and repeat it, to end up to a solution that reflects the intended purpose. New findings from testing can help redefine the problem, adjust the prototypes, or generate new ideas. Through this iterative learning, solutions become more refined and user-centred.

Design Thinking is especially useful for ClimaGen Living Labs as they work to co-create community-centred NBS in socially vulnerable or environmentally stressed neighbourhoods. It can help create a deep understanding of the community context and lived experiences, to ultimately bring the relevant actors on board and support them with the final co-created solution. This process helps the Living Lab teams to create a structured and inclusive approach to the facilitation of diverse stakeholder inputs, and through iterative processes, improve the concepts before implementation. It can also support maintaining transparency and trust-building through processes, and an early identification of risks, assumptions, challenges and political or social issues.

For Design Thinking to be effective, each stage requires adequate time and attention. Living Lab representatives should ensure that co-creation formats are inclusive, accessible and adapted to local realities, and that feedback loops, both open and anonymous, are in place. The methodology is not linear, as success depends on the willingness to return to previous stages, refine insights, and keep the user experience central throughout the process.

4.4 Methods and Tools

The selection of co-creation methods and tools within each ClimaGen Living Lab should be grounded in its local context, needs and constraints. No single method or toolkit is universally applicable. Instead, each ClimaGen Living Lab is expected to adapt its approach based on its stakeholders, social dynamics, governance structure, political environment, available resources, and the specific characteristics of the neighbourhoods targeted for intervention.

ClimaGen Living Labs apply co-creation methods and tools at different stages and for various purposes. These include early phases of problem exploration and stakeholder engagement, the co-design and development of solutions, real-life experimentation and testing, and later stages of reflection, learning, and adaptation. While the specific tools used in each phase may differ, cities must document how co-creation contributes to decision-making and how stakeholder perspectives are implemented. This ensures that, despite methodological variation, Living Labs remain aligned with the core principles of inclusiveness, transparency, experimentation, and shared ownership.

To guide this process, **Table 5** organises tested and openly accessible co-creation methods and tools according to the type of resource and content. These resources are relevant to ClimaGen's objectives and were selected because they:

- Place citizens at the centre of decision-making
- Address co-creation in vulnerable neighbourhoods
- Support the co-design and implementation of NbS, and/or
- Provide structured approaches to experimentation and stakeholder engagement

Several of the listed resources are directly aligned with commitments referenced in the ClimaGen DoA. Specifically, the UNaLab toolkit and NbS catalogue will be updated with ClimaGen’s generated outcomes to strengthen and expand the existing repository. Through ENoLL, documented Living Lab practices, exploitable results, and evidence generated within ClimaGen will be integrated into the UNaLab knowledge base, contributing to the broader European evidence base for urban nature-based living labs.

In a similar way, the CommuniCity resources build on experience in engaging vulnerable neighbourhoods in urban co-creation processes, while the SCORE toolkit provides approaches tailored to urban governance contexts. Other materials included in the table contribute methodologies for participatory planning and environmental interventions.

It should be noted that the resources listed in Table 5 originate from a variety of projects and organisations. While the table provides an overview of selected methods and toolkits that may support ClimaGen Living Lab activities, the intellectual property rights of the individual tools remain with their respective owners. In most cases, the toolkits compile multiple methods developed by different contributors, each subject to its own attribution and usage conditions. Some tools included in the table, such as the Living Lab Mapping Canvas developed by ENoLL, are made available free of charge for use within the ClimaGen project and its Living Lab activities. However, the underlying methodology, background knowledge, and intellectual property remain the property of ENoLL and are not intended for commercial reuse or external exploitation beyond the scope of the project.

These resources serve as guidance rather than prescribing a specific process. Cities may use them as inspiration, directly apply tools, or adapt them to fit their context. In WP2, and particularly T2.1, selected tools from the table are introduced and tried-out during ClimaLabs Joint Learning Sessions. During these sessions, cities work hands-on on specific methodologies (such as stakeholder mapping, co-design templates or governance canvases), adapting them to their local Living Lab plans. Beyond WP2, relevant cross-cutting partners may also draw upon these tools in Tasks 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.2, 4.1 and 4.2 when engaging with cities.

In this way, the table supports not only local Living Lab activities, but also internal co-creation processes within the consortium. Additions to the list will be made as necessary based on the insights gained during these activities.

Through this combination of resources, structured capacity-building, cross-WP integration, and reflective documentation, ClimaGen ensures that tool selection is purposeful, aligned with project objectives, and operationally embedded within the Living Lab methodology applied by the cities.

Project or Initiative	Type of Resource	Content	Owner	IP	Link
UNaLab	Toolkit	Tools and methods for co-creation related to NbS.	ENoLL (toolkit compilation), tools © respective owners	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://unalab.enoll.org/
	Handbook	NBS Technical Handbook Factsheets.	Institut für Landschaftsplanung und Ökologie - ILPÖ	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://unalab.eu/system/files/2022-11/unalab-nbs-technical-handbook-factsheets2022-11-17.pdf
	Tool	The Living Lab Mapping Canvas.	ENoLL (developed within the URBANOME and UNaLab projects)	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/eu-valorisation-policy/knowledge-valorisation-platform/repository/living-labs-harmonization-framework-and-mapping-canvas-scalable-approach-collaborative-open
	Handbook	Living Lab Handbook for Urban Living Labs developing NbS.	Luleå University of Technology, ENoLL	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://unalab.eu/system/files/2020-07/living-lab-handbook2020-07-09.pdf
CommuniCity	Toolkit	Methodologies, tools and toolkits on co-creation with vulnerable neighbourhoods, and ethics and inclusivity framework.	ENoLL (platform), tools © respective owners	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://communilab.eu/methodologies-tools-and-toolkits/

SCORE	Toolkit	Urban development co-creation tools. This toolkit is accompanied with guidelines and instructions (second link) of when and how to use the tools.	Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies of Erasmus University Rotterdam	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://www.ihs.nl/en/advisory-and-training/tools-and-toolkits/co-create-your-city-toolkit/toolkit https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Pilot-Operational-Plans.pdf
NESTA	Toolkit	Collective Intelligence Design Playbook. Tools, tactics and methods for community engagement tackling global challenges.	Nesta	Attribution required; non-commercial use; share alike	https://www.nesta.org.uk/toolkit/collective-intelligence-design-playbook/
IDEO.org	Toolkit	The field guide to human-centered design through co-creation tools.	IDEO.org	Attribution required; non-commercial use; no derivatives	https://www.designkit.org/resources/1.html
SISCODE	Toolkit	Co-creation methods for facilitators.	SISCODE project consortium	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://siscodoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/toolkit-27092019-1.pdf
18F Methods	Toolkit	Collection of tools for human-centered design.	18F	Public domain	https://guides.18f.org/methods/
SEI	Tool	MapStakes. A tool for mapping, involving and monitoring stakeholders in co-creation processes.	Stockholm Environment Institute	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://www.sei.org/publications/mapstakes-tool-mapping-stakeholders/

Board of Innovation	Toolkit	Tools for innovation. Best fit for the ideation and testing stages of the process.	Board of Innovation	Attribution required; non-commercial use; share alike	https://www.boardofinnovation.com/tools/
Service Design Tools	Toolkit	Co-design tools for several stages in the process.	oblo.design	Attribution required; non-commercial use; no derivatives	https://servicedesigntools.org/tools
GILL	Toolkit	Practical tools designed to help new entrepreneurs with a gendered perspective.	ENoLL (toolkit), tools © respective owners	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://gillhub.eu/explore/toolbox/
UTMC Platform	Knowledge repository	Resources, publications, guidelines and tools to accelerate urban, climate-focused progress.	ENoLL (content compilation), tools © respective owners	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://urbantransitionsmision.org/centre/
Living-in.EU Knowledge Base	Knowledge repository	Webinars, courses, articles, reports and more on citizen-centring urban digital transition.	ENoLL (content compilation), tools © respective owners	Attribution required; non-commercial use	https://living-in.eu/knowledge-base

Table 5 Preliminary co-creation methods and tools catalogue. IP conditions summarise the main usage requirements of each resource. Users should consult the original source for full licensing details.

5. KPIs & Monitoring Framework

ClimaGen Living Labs operate in complex, real-life urban contexts where learning, adaptation, and continuous improvement are essential. Monitoring and reflection, therefore, play an important role in helping them understand how their activities evolve, how stakeholders engage with them, and how their actions contribute to broader objectives. Monitoring and measurement can support learning, informed decision-making, and the strengthening of Living Lab practices. Experiences and learnings will be discussed in future ClimaLabs Experience Reports (D2.2, D2.4, D2.6).

Within the overall project structure, this section shares the monitoring options for Living Lab activities. It outlines key evaluation dimensions aligned with ClimaGen principles and proposes indicative KPIs that help reflection. In parallel, the core project-wide impact monitoring is being developed under WP3 and focuses on tracking progress towards project objectives, including the increase in greening and user satisfaction in targeted areas. Elements of this monitoring, particularly those related to stakeholder engagement and satisfaction with interventions, may overlap with aspects of Living Lab activity and can inform reflections on Living Lab performance. The detailed definition of those indicators, baselines, responsibilities, and data collection processes will be addressed in D3.3 (ClimaGen Impact Model Definition 1) and developed in close collaboration with the cities.

In this sense, D2.1 provides the conceptual approach for monitoring Living Lab performance, while D3.3 provides an evaluation framework at project level. Cities are expected to establish baselines and contribute to project-wide monitoring under WP3, while separately considering the evaluation dimensions presented here to reflect on the quality and maturity of their Living Lab practices.

The monitoring considerations and KPIs in this chapter are suggested as indicative and supportive, rather than mandatory. They offer cities a structured way to think about what aspects of their Living Lab activities they may wish to observe, document, or reflect upon during and beyond the project. These considerations can help cities identify learning needs, support internal discussions on governance and engagement, and align Living Lab activities with broader ClimaGen impact pathways, while allowing flexibility to adapt monitoring efforts to local capacities and priorities.

Finally, reference is made to the Living Lab labelling and certification process coordinated by ENoLL, which offers an additional benchmark for assessing the quality and maturity of Living Lab operations. In ClimaGen, obtaining formal ENoLL certification is not an objective or requirement. The reference serves to situate ClimaGen Living Labs within the broader Living Lab ecosystem and to provide an optional maturity reference. Some participating cities may already operate certified Living Labs, and further information on the status and characteristics of individual Living Labs is provided in the respective city descriptions.

5.1 Evaluation considerations for ClimaGen Living Labs

Over time, the Living Lab community has recognised the need for a structured method to reflect on Living Lab maturity, performance and impact, while still respecting the contextual differences between initiatives. In response, recent work by Vervoort et al. (2024)²⁴, currently applied within ENoLL, has proposed a harmonised evaluation framework that brings together common evaluation dimensions used across Living Labs.

²⁴ Vervoort, K., Konstantinidis, E., Desole, M., Onur, O., Trousse, B., Woodcock, A., Garatea, J., Petsani, D., Ponomareva, A., Roset Pérez, B., Gamboa, G., & Bamidis, P. (2024, June 11). A harmonized assessment method and KPIs for evaluating Living Labs. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11581077>

ENoLL is currently the only entity certifying Living Labs through a structured evaluation process²⁵ combining quantitative self-assessment and qualitative peer review. While ClimaGen Living Labs are not required to undergo formal certification during the project, the principles of this process offer guidance for reflection and improvement.

For ClimaGen Living Labs this framework is not a mandatory evaluation or certification requirement. Instead, it serves as a reference point to reflect on how Living Labs are organised, governed, and developed over time. Having a shared set of evaluation dimensions, ClimaGen Living Labs can better situate their local practices within the broader Living Lab landscape, while remaining fully responsive to their specific contexts. In practice, ClimaGen cities may use these evaluation dimensions and KPIs at key moments of their processes, such as during the initial set-up phase, after major co-creation or pilot implementation activities, or when reflecting on progress at project milestones.

The 34 general Living Lab KPIs presented in **Table 6** are part of the harmonised evaluation framework. In the context of ClimaGen, Living Labs are not expected to monitor all indicators. Instead, the framework can help cities identify which aspects of Living Lab organisation and operation are most relevant to their current development stage and local priorities. These will be revisited in the future Living Lab Experience reports.

Chapter	Criteria	KPI
Strategy	Governance	<p>% of (active) involvement of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the development of the vision/mission of the Living Lab (e.g., all Q4 represented is 100%)</p> <p>% of participation of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the governance of the Living Lab (strategic & operational roles and decision-making processes)</p> <p>Presence of partner agreements/ arrangements for co-innovation</p> <p>Completeness of a strategic roadmap for the Living Lab (SMART goals, responsibilities, and decision-making processes)</p>
	Business model	<p>Completeness of the described business model approach (value proposition, problems & solutions, activities & resources, key stakeholders, customers, users, costs & revenues, metrics & impacts)</p> <p>Number of (different) services offered by the Living Lab (e.g. stakeholder engagement) covering (all) different phases of the innovation lifecycle</p>

²⁵ ENoLL Labelling and Certification. (2025, November 26). ENoLL. <https://enoll.org/enoll-labelling-and-certification/>
D2.1 ClimaLabs Framework Definition

	Culture & collaboration	<p>Presence of internal & external business & client relation management process/strategy (including contracts)</p> <p>Frequency of internal communication & results sharing to keep partners informed & aligned</p> <p>Number of regional, national & international collaborations beyond the scope of an individual Living Lab project</p>
Operations	Human resources	% of implementation of needed internal roles and responsibilities within the operational Living Lab team in a flexible way (are all roles sufficiently attributed, depending on the size of the operational Living Lab team)
	Operations	<p>Time spent within successfully completed projects and/or activities related to the Living Lab (how many weeks/months/years of experience does the Living Lab has in running projects and or activities)</p> <p>Completeness & frequency of internal self-monitoring processes (how often are the Living Lab essential parts of their organisation: strategic, financial, equipment & infrastructure, policy, project outcomes)</p>
	Equipment & infrastructure	<p>% of accessibility in time to facilities (e.g. offices, cocreation spaces, test facilities...)</p> <p>% of accessibility in time to hard- & software (e.g. cocreation materials, computers, wearables, interaction software, polling/ survey software...)</p>
Openness	Innovation, partnerships, projects & processes	<p>% of implementation needed processes to safeguard a reflective and iterative approach to transdisciplinary collaboration</p> <p>% of implementation of needed processes to safeguard an ethical approach (e.g. regulatory requirements, data protection needed etc.)</p>
	Ownership of results	<p>% of implementation of needed rules & regulations regarding the use, sharing & licensing of data and IP of collaborative outcomes</p> <p>% of implementation of user agreements (data, IPR, rights, liabilities)</p>

Users & reality	User centrality	<p>% of diversity of stakeholders involved as end-users in Living Lab projects and/or activities</p> <p>Degree of influence end-users exert on the different phases of the innovation lifecycle (from informing to empowerment)</p>
	Lifecycle & real-life	<p>Degree of involvement of end-users in the different phases of the innovation lifecycle (e.g. problem space, solution space, implementation space)</p> <p>Degree of use of real-life contexts of users in the different phases of the innovation lifecycle</p>
	Tools & methods	<p>Degree of appropriateness of tools & methods used for the different phases of the innovation lifecycle</p> <p>Frequency of external communication & results sharing to keep end-users and external stakeholders informed and engaged</p>
Value & impact	(Co-created) values	<p>% of satisfaction of users/stakeholders (from the whole value chain) concerning their involvement/influence on the innovation lifecycle</p> <p>% of satisfaction of users/stakeholders concerning knowledge sharing & Capacity Building (learning materials & infrastructures)</p> <p>Number of relevant (open) educational resources (including datasets, trainings) shared/provided for relevant stakeholders</p>
	Impact(s)	<p>Completeness and frequency of impact assessments (how often is the Living Lab monitoring different types of impacts they are generating: societal, environmental, economic, regulatory, academic, technological)</p>
Stability & harmonisation	Stability	<p>% of increase in number of relationships (with a reliable partner network and customers)</p> <p>Level of financial sustainability based on a balanced & diversified set of funding (structural vs. project-based) & revenue streams</p> <p>Number of living lab value propositions, flexible to adapt to new circumstances</p>

	Harmonisation & scale-up	<p>% of increase in number of partners committed to scale up products/ solutions/ services</p> <p>Number of products/solutions/services (able to be) scaled up</p> <p>Number of participations in (cross-border/cross-sectoral) initiatives/projects based on harmonized Living Lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools, processes, or services</p>
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Table 6 Reference KPIs for Living Labs. Adapted from Vervoort, et al (2024).

While ClimaGen Living Labs share a common focus on climate innovation and impact, each operates in a unique context with distinct stakeholders, challenges and capacities. To ensure both comparability and diversity, this monitoring approach integrates, in addition to the above chapters and criteria, the different types of impact that can inform the development of KPIs.

The impact dimensions and indicative KPIs presented in **Table 7** are optional and adaptable references for ClimaGen Living Labs. They are aimed to support cities in reflecting on the types of impact their Living Lab activities aim to generate during and beyond the project, and in identifying measurable parameters that can inform learning and improvement over time. These impact dimensions will also be considered by project partners when defining ClimaGen-specific monitoring parameters under Deliverable D3.3, where project-level impact pathways and indicators are further elaborated.

Type of Impact	KPI
Societal	<p>Number or proportion of participants reporting increased awareness or understanding of climate-resilient regeneration topics</p> <p>Self-reported adoption of new practices or behaviours related to climate adaptation, mitigation, or sustainable use of public space among Living Lab participants</p> <p>Perceived changes in well-being or quality of life associated with Living Lab interventions</p> <p>Number of implemented solutions responding to local challenges & opportunities</p>
Environmental	<p>Number or proportion of participants reporting increased awareness of environmental and climate-related issues addressed by the Living Lab</p> <p>Increased access to and use of green and blue infrastructure created or enhanced through Living Lab interventions</p>

Economic	<p>Number of (new) businesses created/supported (e.g. spinoffs/start-ups)</p> <p>Number of financing partners engaged in activities</p> <p>Number of workshops/dialogues/activities conducted with the cities regarding projects' funding and financing</p> <p>Number of intellectual property outputs formally registered or exploited (e.g. patents, licences, open-source tools, methodologies, or replication-ready solutions)</p> <p>Number of development risks identified, discussed, or mitigated through Living Lab co-creation and testing activities</p> <p>Evidence of avoided redesign, delays, or implementation changes due to early testing within the Living Lab</p>
Regulatory	<p>Number of adapted/implemented policies and/or directives with input from Living Lab activities</p> <p>Number of participants reporting improved dialogue and shared understanding between political representatives and innovation ecosystem actors as a result of project activities.</p>
Academic	<p>Number of peer-reviewed scientific papers and/or publications/articles</p> <p>Number of citations or other recognised academic impact indicators associated with these publications</p>
Technological	<p>% of increase in Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of innovated technologies</p> <p>Number of technologies implemented in the market</p>

Table 7 Indicative impact dimensions and KPIs relevant to ClimaGen Living Labs. Adapted from Vervoort, et al (2024)

Within ClimaGen, ENOLL's role is to help cities understand how evaluation dimensions and KPIs can be used in a proportionate and context-sensitive way. This includes supporting reflection on Living Lab maturity, governance, stakeholder engagement, and learning processes, rather than conducting formal assessments or audits. By selectively using the evaluation dimensions and KPI categories presented in this chapter, ClimaGen Living Labs can strengthen transparency, support learning, and improve the sustainability of their activities beyond the project lifetime. This reflective approach also supports peer learning across cities and facilitates connections with the wider Living Lab community, without imposing additional reporting or certification obligations.

6. Key considerations for ClimaGen Living Labs

Although real-life experimentation is essential to ClimaGen’s approach, implementing and testing NbS in complex urban and socially vulnerable contexts presents practical challenges for the cities. These challenges are not barriers, but opportunities to improve processes and strengthen the impact of interventions. Insights gathered from the cross-city exchanges, including ClimaLab and sense-making sessions in Trondheim (April 2025) and Gernika (October 2025), the city survey and the follow-up online workshop (10 October 2025), have helped identify anticipated challenges that may shape how ClimaGen Living Labs operate over the course of the project.

While these considerations vary across local contexts, several common patterns have emerged. These are summarised in **Figure 9** and discussed in the paragraphs below along with suggested methodological responses to guide cities.

Figure 9 Anticipated challenges reported by ClimaGen cities

6.1 Financial and Resource Constraints

Limited funding and financial resources are a frequent challenge. Cities face difficulties in securing sufficient operational budgets beyond ClimaGen, moving from preparation to realisation, and maintaining interventions over the long term. Generating direct revenue from NbS remains challenging, limiting interest from commercial investors and complicating the quantification and monetisation of value. In addition, some cities reported that while budgets are available for planning, there is often insufficient funding for implementation, reducing the speed of delivering tangible results.

ClimaGen Living Labs should treat financial stability as an integral design parameter rather than a consideration. Cities can leverage capacity-building and guidance on partnership models through T2.1, explore financing and partnership models for the greening measures through T2.3, and prioritise early demonstration of NbS to attract stakeholder support and investment. Structured financial planning and transparent reporting can strengthen the case for sustained funding.

6.2 Coordination and Governance Challenges

ClimaGen Living Labs rely on collaboration across the quadruple and quintuple helix. Engaging private companies, investors, and other external stakeholders consistently over time may prove challenging, particularly when agendas diverge or when long-term commitment is uncertain.

Fragmented departmental structures, political volatility or limited political support can further complicate the continuity and prioritisation of NbS interventions, as well as resource constraints, unclear roles or misaligned expectations.

To avoid such challenges, ClimaGen Living Labs should adopt explicit governance structures that provide a clear definition of leadership, roles, and responsibilities. Project support through *City Dialogues*, *Joint Learning Sessions* and iterative consultation processes, can help align priorities and expectations. Cross-departmental workshops, use of the ClimaGen framework, and integration of lessons from peer cities can improve coordination and sustain momentum despite political changes.

6.3 Community and Stakeholder Engagement

Engaging residents and local stakeholders in co-creation processes can be challenging, particularly in socially vulnerable neighbourhoods. Cities noted difficulties in maintaining long-term participation, preventing engagement fatigue, and gaining trust, especially where previous promises have gone unmet, and there is limited trust in public authorities. Low awareness, lack of understanding of NbS, and gaps in reaching specific groups, such as youth, may further limit meaningful participation. Some cities also reported challenges in understanding how best to involve residents and in ensuring that small-scale projects are anchored for long-term sustainability. Although stakeholder engagement is already taking place through workshops, surveys, public consultations, partnerships with NGOs, schools, and neighbourhood associations, only one city reported full confidence in understanding community needs. Four cities expressed low confidence, and the remaining cities indicated only partial confidence. Strengthening this understanding is essential, as accurate insights into community priorities and vulnerabilities are a precondition for meaningful co-creation and for ensuring that real-life experimentation produces relevant, accepted, and socially beneficial outcomes.

Applying participatory co-creation methods, inclusive outreach strategies, and continuous engagement mechanisms can strengthen trust and community ownership. Sharing tangible examples of successful NbS, linking interventions to residents' priorities, and integrating feedback loops can enhance social acceptance and ensure interventions remain impactful for the community. ClimaGen Living Labs should emphasise iterative engagement cycles and adaptive communication strategies based on monitoring results, ensuring that participation quality evolves over time.

6.4 Technical, Knowledge, and Capacity Limitations

Many cities anticipate internal capacity limitations that may affect the ability to carry out experimentation effectively. These include limited staff time, insufficient expertise in climate resilience or co-creation methodologies, and restricted access to data, technological tools and methodological guidance. This can affect the quality of planning, experimentation, and monitoring.

Throughout the project, capacity-building activities, training modules, and access to tested co-creation methods and tools can help staff and partners build the required knowledge and technical skills. Collaboration with universities, think-tanks, and other cities can also support knowledge exchange and fill expertise gaps. Through *ClimaLabs Joint Learning Sessions* capacity-building is a continuous target through trainings, peer exchange, and methodological guidance.

6.5 Spatial and Regulatory Constraints

A lack of available and affordable physical space, competing land uses, and adverse ownership structures were reported as significant challenges. Legal and regulatory frameworks, such as land-use restrictions or coordination with utility providers, may further hinder implementation. Existing environmental degradation or site-specific pollution can increase costs or limit the effectiveness of NbS.

To overcome physical constraints, early identification of suitable sites, careful integration of land-use and regulatory considerations, and creative spatial solutions can help. Coordinating with multiple stakeholders and leveraging municipal partnerships can support access to land and resources, while careful planning ensures NbS deliver lasting environmental benefits.

6.6 Measuring Effectiveness and Impact

Cities expressed concerns about the lack of standardised methods to measure and demonstrate the effectiveness and benefits of NbS, including satisfaction, social impact, and environmental improvements. Without consistent monitoring, adjusting strategies and assessing long-term outcomes can be challenging.

Context-specific KPIs and monitoring processes, as suggested in this framework, provide a flexible reference for tracking progress. By reflecting on these indicators over time, ClimaGen Living Labs can improve outreach, refine interventions, and strengthen their performance. Coordination under WP3 and D3.3 (ClimaGen Impact Model) will further ensure that monitoring aligns with project-level objectives and broader climate goals.

Together, these challenges can affect cities' ability to design and test NbS in the real urban environment. They may slow down implementation, limit iteration cycles, or create barriers to achieving community ownership, all of which are essential for successful climate adaptation and for ensuring sustained impact beyond the duration of the project. ClimaGen's approach is structured to help cities navigate these barriers through the Framework's implementation meetings, ClimaLabs Joint Learning Sessions, City Dialogues, Sense-Making Sessions, and the project's Guidance Package, cities will receive tools, practical methodologies, capacity-building support, and access to peer learning across the consortium. This integrated support aims to strengthen internal capacity, improve cross-collaboration, enhance engagement processes, and provide better access to knowledge, data, and methods.

7. Conclusion

This Framework provides cities with a shared reference for setting up and operating ClimaGen Living Labs as practical, inclusive, and future-oriented structures. It translates the project's ambition into a common conceptual and organisational model that supports alignment across cities, without prescribing uniform implementation pathways. Cities enter the process from different starting points, influenced by different governance systems, capacities, and community dynamics. In line with Living Lab principles, the ClimaGen model enables local adaptation while maintaining a shared set of principles.

This document establishes the structural foundations that help cities frame their Living Lab processes and priorities. The practical navigation of implementation realities, such as cross-departmental collaboration, community engagement, technical capacity, access to data, and learning from experimentation, is supported through project mechanisms including City Dialogues, Sense-Making Sessions, hands-on workshops, and the iterative development of city-specific practices. In this way, ClimaGen Living Labs function also as interconnected learning environments that enable reflection, knowledge sharing, and improvement across the consortium.

The ClimaLabs Framework brings together the conceptual foundations of Living Labs and the ClimaGen cities' ambitions to shape climate-resilient regeneration. It shows how Living Labs, as open and user-centred innovation ecosystems, can support cities in tackling complex urban challenges by combining real-life experimentation with strong community involvement. Central characteristics such as multi-stakeholder participation, iterative testing, orchestration across institutional levels, and the use of diverse methods create the basis for adaptive and inclusive experimentation. This Framework aimed to translate these principles into a ClimaGen-specific approach.

Across the document, the common characteristics and values of ClimaGen Living Labs emerge. Cities align their ClimaGen Living Labs with local governance structures, combine digital and low-tech engagement methods, and link ecological measures with cultural, social and economic co-benefits. Environmental value is reflected in actions that strengthen biodiversity, cooling, and ecosystem health; cultural value in the recognition of local identity, heritage and creativity; economic value in new opportunities for local business and community-driven initiatives; and innovation value in the shared learning processes that improve decision-making and support evidence-based policies. These values guide each city's work while leaving room for local adaptation and specific priorities.

The Framework also brings together the insights and challenges that cities anticipate as they move into real-life experimentation. Limited staff time, lack of physical space, fragmented governance and administrative barriers can slow progress, while uneven access to data and technology complicates planning and monitoring. Cities also expect difficulties in keeping communities and private actors engaged over the long term, especially when scaling actions beyond the initial neighbourhood. At the same time, cities recognise the importance of improving their understanding of community needs and strengthening inclusive engagement practices. The Framework highlights how a diverse portfolio of co-creation methods can support cities in addressing these issues by improving collaboration and strengthening reflection and learning.

Finally, the Framework also captures the initial status of the ClimaGen Living Labs in the Annex, as activities have been ongoing or planned during its development. Early co-creation activities show a

wide mix of formats, from arts-led engagement and citizen science to spatial mapping and hands-on prototyping, tailored to local cultures and challenges. This first status description will help to provide an evolving picture of how the ClimaLabs are taking shape on the ground and how they will continue to develop throughout the project. Taken together, the concepts, values, structures and early experiences outlined in this document form a shared foundation for the ClimaGen cities, enabling mutual learning and collective support throughout their co-creation process.

Annex A

ClimaGen Living Labs in practice

This chapter provides an overview of the ClimaGen Living Labs as they are evolving across the demonstration and replicator cities. It presents a snapshot of their ClimaGen activities from 2025 up to January 2026 and anticipated upcoming actions through June 2026. For each city, the description covers the local context, selected intervention areas, and the current status of co-creation processes. Beyond documenting actions taken, the chapter also shares the encountered challenges, insights, and early lessons emerging from local implementation.

The purpose of this section is twofold. First, it serves as a practical record of how each ClimaGen Living Lab is progressing within its own context and constraints. Second, it provides reflection points that support improvement. By capturing both achievements and difficulties, this material contributes to monitoring activities across the project and enables cities to adjust, refine, and strengthen their Living Lab practices as implementation advances.

These insights have informed the design of the *ClimaLabs Joint Learning Sessions*, which aim to support cities in establishing and running their Living Labs, while also fostering peer-to-peer exchange and collaboration among the nine cities and project partners.

For all cities, detailed descriptions will be published in the upcoming ClimaGen City Reports later in 2026. The ClimaLabs Experience Reports, also upcoming, will build on the development and reflections captured in this initial review.

Demonstration cities

Belgrade, Serbia

Short description of the area:

Belgrade selected the former railway corridor in Dorćol as the site for its new Linear Park project. Following the railway's relocation and the area's abandonment, the city decided in 2018 to invest €82 million (between 2023 and 2025) to transform the 4.5 km stretch into a green corridor for urban regeneration.

Short description of the objective for the area:

Belgrade plans to co-create and implement community greening in the Linear Park and nearby areas, expanding these collaborative methods to other industrial regeneration zones. Through ClimaGen-funded initiatives, the city aims to re-green old residential and educational blocks near the park, including the Marina Dorćol and Silosi neighbourhoods. About 2,650 m² of neglected green spaces around older housing will be restored, featuring up to 50 gardens of at least 50 m² each, along with bioretention zones, community gardens, micro-forests, and therapeutic gardens. In addition, after an open call, an artistic intervention will be established and carried out, through a participatory process involving interdisciplinary, art and science and citizen science practices. These new green spaces will form an interconnected urban network, linking the Linear Park with the surrounding city and the Danube riverbank. Overall, the project seeks to foster dialogue and co-creation among residents, existing landscapes, new housing developments, and public green spaces.

Lessons and Challenges from Practice:

Challenges in co-creation activities: The political situation is very critical at this moment in the whole country. People are not concerned about this project’s activities or possible impact, considering the more urgent challenges that they face. There is a lot of tension in the area that has been influencing the project’s activities. This also leads to an increasing lack of trust for further developments.

Reflections and lessons-learnt: Being adaptable is key to this situation, when in touch with both the administration of the city and the citizens. The ClimaGen team must ensure that they avoid giving the impression that they aim to distract citizens from other, more serious issues, or even of greenwashing.

Activity	Past – Ongoing – Planned	Target group(s) (Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society)
Belgrade supporting partners have been involved in numerous projects, initiatives and events deploying different co-creative approaches and methodologies.	Past	All
Consultation for urban plans in September 2025	Past	Public / Private
The city’s ability to implement co-created solutions must be ensured, otherwise it will not have a prominent role in the co-creation activities with citizens. This is depending on the upcoming developments and the resolution of the political situation at a national and local level, and how the citizens will perceive this initiative.	Future	All

Table 8 Overview of the Co-creation Activities in Belgrade

Gdańsk, Poland

Short description of the area:

The Gdańsk ClimaGen demonstrator takes the form of two green corridors that span the city centre and the post-shipyard area, also known as the Young City — a postindustrial and partly residential district with a strong cultural and historical identity as the birthplace of the Solidarity movement. The area, bordered by the river and a railway line and close to the historic city centre, is characterised by cultural landmarks such as the European Solidarity Centre and the Museum of the Second World War. However, the district remains fragmented and underused, with limited green space (around 10%) and weak spatial and social connections between old and new developments. The Radunia Canal, currently lacking public accessibility, offers potential for blue-green infrastructure that reconnects people to the waterfront. The regeneration of the area will build on its cultural significance and ongoing redevelopment to create a network of green corridors, small parks, and public spaces that encourage community use and co-management.

Short description of the objective for the area:

Within the ClimaGen framework, the city will establish a ClimaLab as a platform for participatory design and decision-making, inviting stakeholders to co-develop pathways, pocket parks, waterfront parks, and squares that reconnect the post-shipyard with the wider urban fabric. Co-creation activities will include participatory workshops, mapping of interests and stakeholders, and joint planning of green interventions that balance industrial heritage, housing, and cultural life. These actions will be complemented by collaborative monitoring of environmental impacts and the testing of nature-based solutions such as bioretention beds, permeable paths, renaturalisation and land art areas. Through this process, Gdańsk seeks to build a new shared identity for the area, transforming it into a vibrant, climate-resilient neighbourhood, while ensuring social inclusion and preventing gentrification through collective decision-making and community-led placemaking.

Lessons and Challenges from Practice:

Challenges in co-creation activities: Engaging start-ups in co-creation has proven difficult, given their changing priorities and limited resources, while keeping deadlines and fiscal risks linked to project implementation and long-term impact require constant attention and mitigation. Bureaucratic procedures within local authorities are also limiting the testing and adaptation period of the innovation.

Reflections and lessons-learned: New ideas are always emerging with new collaborations and the team working on the co-creation activities is essential. Structuring the project as a research process supports flexibility and learning. Attention should be given to embracing new ideas from collaborations and thinking beyond the project's scope, while remaining open to different durations and intensities of stakeholder engagement. At the same time, in response to the difficulty of engaging start-ups in co-creation on a sustained basis (due to shifting priorities and limited resources), activities involving youth and start-ups could be reoriented toward fostering entrepreneurship among young people and students—for example by organizing hackathons around ClimaGen's thematic challenges and/or by partnering with organizations that already have established structures for running competitions, incubating ideas, and supporting start-up creation. This format makes it easier to engage participants in shorter, intensive cycles, while also generating tangible prototypes and solutions that can be further tested.

Activity	Past – Ongoing – Planned	Target group(s) (Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society)
The city adopted an official method of participation called Gdańsk Project Workshop, through which they conducted many participatory workshops, consultations on various topics and in various scales - from micro urban interventions to creating briefs of City Strategies that were used in official works of municipality's lawmaking.	Past	All
Develop collaboration Framework	Past	Partners
Establishment of the project's tech baseline (what can happen and what cannot happen)	Past	Partners
Student engagement for concept development	Past	Academia
Workshops with individual stakeholders	Ongoing – Planned	All
Opportunities workshops	Present	All
25% Baseline project	Present	All
Going outside the project to ensure longevity of the outputs	Future	All
Mapping opportunities through meetings with individual stakeholders	Future	All

Table 9 Overview of the Co-creation Activities in Gdańsk

Tartu, Estonia

Short description of the area:

Tartu has chosen the regeneration areas in the Annelinn district as its main demonstration site. Annelinn is a residential neighbourhood from the Soviet occupation era, built in the 1970s and consisting mainly of 5- and 9-story apartment buildings. It is a historically significant district where Soviet urban design contrasts sharply with modern urban planning approaches. Nearly one-third of the city's population lives in Annelinn, making it one of Tartu's most densely populated areas. Although the district was originally designed to include multiple functions, many planned infrastructures and amenities were never completed by the Soviets. As a result, Annelinn became a densely built, monofunctional "sleeping district" characterised by low-quality green spaces often called "green deserts." These areas are poorly connected to nature due to the surrounding high-traffic roads. Within the defined green area, approximately 43% of the land consists of this type of low-quality greenery. Local housing associations, formed by residents, will be encouraged to initiate renovation projects and redesign outdoor spaces. The city aims to implement inclusive regeneration and renaturing actions to address pluvial flooding, reduce heat islands, enhance biodiversity connectivity and improve the greenery and urban space for the local community, particularly in the Kaunase and Kalda Street areas.

Short description of the objective for the area:

The ClimaGen project in Tartu will pilot a large-scale greening initiative in a 40-hectare demonstration area, focusing on revitalising about 10 hectares through co-created urban regeneration solutions. A complementary project, LIFE urbanLIFECircles, is already addressing biodiversity connectivity and ecosystem services in Annelinn. European funds, including from projects H2020 oPEN Lab and LIFE IP BuildEST, are helping Tartu upgrade post-war residential blocks toward positive energy neighbourhoods and are largely centred around Annelinn as well.

ClimaGen will co-create innovative nature-based solutions with housing associations, public organisations such as the local library and youth centre, and creative industries, using a user-centred approach to address local climate adaptation and regeneration needs. A comprehensive baseline survey with residents and district-level climate modelling will guide priorities and inform an action plan with community engagement and simulation activities. The city will also experiment with collective ownership models for shared spaces to foster cooperation and community action. Tartu will pioneer the use of gamification and start-up programs to engage young innovators in designing and testing nature-based solutions in Annelinn's living lab. Finally, a Local Community Agreement will be developed to define shared goals, cooperation models, and monitoring practices, linking community ambitions with the Tartu Sustainable Climate and Energy Action Plan (SECAP) and the 100 Climate Neutral Cities initiative.

Lessons and Challenges from Practice:

Challenges in co-creation activities: Civil society consists of many individuals who have conflicting views and needs. Their awareness and attitudes are also very diverse. They can be very reactive when any changes are proposed, without contributing alternatives to the solution - "Do something but not THAT." They could also be characterised as NIMBYs (Not In My Back Yard), which is due to their opposition to local developments or infrastructure in their area. Another challenge is measuring satisfaction qualitatively. For this purpose, a comprehensive survey will be conducted among local residents that aims to measure the current baseline satisfaction with the neighbourhood by using Likert scales.

Lessons-learnt: The opposition of locals to proposals could be settled when different discussion techniques are adapted on a case-by-case basis. There is a need to discuss and for them to conceptualise the broader context of development and change in the city and district, but also their role in it. Additionally, the benefits need to be clearly communicated - even those that may seem common sense. Where needed, awareness-raising and educational activities (especially when it comes to climate change and resilience) may also be necessary.

Activity	Past – Ongoing – Planned	Target group(s) (Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society)	Additional comments/links
Tartu has long-standing experience in engaging residents in urban projects, both for local and international urban development projects. This includes urban planning which heavily relies on citizen consultations and input, the annual participatory budgeting, which empowers citizens to submit their development ideas and that other citizens can vote on, strategic planning (e.g. co-creation in creating the Tartu SECAP); in addition to tens of international projects that have focused on applying various engagement and co-creation models in various projects (https://www.tartu.ee/en/projektid) .	Past	All	
Summer surveys shared among youth (via the local youth center) and locals (via the local library)	Past	Civil Society	
Short street interviews	Past	Civil Society	
Meeting with local organisations including Annelinn Association, Library, Kindergarten, Elderly day centre and others.	Past	Civil Society	These have been both one-on-one and group meetings and workshops.
Co-organizing Annelinn library community day: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Wild play, adventure playground ● Environmental education 	Past	Civil Society	The adventure play was very popular with children.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surveys • Video presentation <p>It aimed to identify the intervention locations, create synergies with other projects and provide input for discussion for two strategy days with the local project team.</p>			
<p>Social media posts, calls to action and a dedicated project newsletter (created by Tartu city gov) are used as channels to share the project's messages, updates, invites, etc with the local people</p>	Ongoing	Civil Society	
<p>Urban nature trails with kindergarten kids x5</p>	Past	Civil Society	Introducing the concept of wild play and nature-based playgrounds to kindergarten children and staff.
<p>Workshop for dream playground with kindergarten kids x1</p>	Past	Civil Society	
<p>Christmas event in the local library</p>	Past	Civil Society	
<p>Hackathon preparatory work for January 2026, together with JA Estonia</p>	Present	Civil Society	
<p>Surveys preparation aiming to establish a satisfaction baseline when it comes to local residents and school children</p>	Present	Civil Society	
<p>Currently, the team is moving from ideation towards co-creation. Upcoming activities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hackathon • Joint mural painting • Joint planting event • Co-creation workshops <p>EAA students installations</p>	Future	Civil Society	

Table 10 Overview of the Co-creation Activities in Tartu

Torino, Italy

Short description of the area:

Torino will use the post-industrial Mirafiori neighbourhood in the south of the city as its main demonstration area. Within this area and together with residents, Torino will create, implement and manage Orti Generali, a large-scale urban food garden project aiming to build a model of social enterprise for the transformation and management of residual agricultural areas. Orti Generali is a remnant of a once more extensive, agricultural landscape and the area has recently been rehabilitated as an urban park (Parco Piemonte). The city aims to connect this historical significance with social equity and ecological sustainability, guided by collaborative and integrated urban planning, supported by augmented reality facilities (SRL 2-9). The reconversion project will help generate positive change in an area with large potential conflicts of interest, to the mutual benefit of the local stakeholders.

Short description of the objective for the area:

Torino has allocated €900k to remove unauthorised gardens and create 100 new, accessible gardens within a 0.5 km² demonstration area. The initiative aligns with the city's Green Infrastructure Strategic Plan and NEB Manifesto, using ClimaGen funding to reinforce riverbanks naturally, plant native trees, and organise a Landscape Festival with the Mirafiori Foundation. Drawing on experience from projects like Conexus, proGReg, and FUSILLI, Torino will strengthen its role as a Living Lab for nature-based solutions and circular food systems. The city will remove spontaneous riverside gardens (funded with €800,000 of its own budget) and expand Orti Generali through €170,000 from Compagnia di San Paolo. Orti Generali will ensure social innovation and regulated urban gardening, while new plantings will enhance the Bela Rosin park and mausoleum area. The Mirafiori Community Foundation and LINKS Foundation will lead stakeholder engagement, cultural heritage events, and youth participation. A recurring Landscape Festival (2026, 2028) will showcase artistic re-naturing installations and connect art, nature, and community.

Lessons and Challenges from Practice:

Challenges in co-creation activities: There are many interconnections between different programmes, and good coordination between people and programmes is necessary. The timing of the works (removal, planting, etc.) is tricky to align with co-creation actions. The same regarding the digital co-creation tool that is being developed by LINKS. It is important to strengthen the link between the two neighbouring cities sharing the riverbanks (Nichelino and Torino). It is challenging yet crucial to ensure systematic data collection, mixing quantitative and qualitative data. Finally, despite the beauty of the area (high percentage of green and water) it is still a challenge to spread the idea of Mirafiori as an NEB location.

Reflections and lessons-learned: NGOs and other organisations can and should support this process. Collaboration channels should be established and reinforced. Constant updates and flexibility is needed to ensure good timing and effective coordination.

Activity	Past – Ongoing – Planned	Target group(s) (Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society)	Additional comments/links
<p>Previous EU projects (involving living labs and co-design), multi-stakeholder working groups, exchange platforms (local, national, international), collaborative policy making, etc have already taken place and have set a good groundwork for the work in ClimaGen.</p>	<p>Past</p>	<p>All</p>	<p>Fondazione Mirafiori, together with the city of Torino, has already implemented co-creation and participatory approaches through several European projects that have tested their actions in the Mirafiori Sud neighbourhood.</p> <p>As part of the proGReg project, the Mirafiori Living Lab involved citizens, local associations and businesses in the co-design and implementation of nature-based solutions, such as community gardens, green corridors and circular economy initiatives aimed at improving environmental quality and social inclusion.</p> <p>In the FUSILLI project, the Living Lab itself continued to serve as a participatory platform to promote sustainable urban food systems. It involved local stakeholders in the joint development of actions related to urban agriculture, nutrition education and short food supply chains, strengthening the role of the community in defining local sustainability strategies.</p>
<p>Walk and talk Co-design Session (July 2025)</p>	<p>Past</p>	<p>All</p>	<p>Assessing the needs and priorities of residents and key stakeholders.</p>
<p>Technical and ONG field trip linked to an artwork (September 2025)</p>	<p>Past</p>	<p>All</p>	
<p>Voci di quartiere – Turin Masterplan Participatory activities (September 2025)</p>	<p>Past</p>	<p>All</p>	<p>Inputs regarding the target area were gathered.</p>

IDOLO Mike Nelson Artwork of the history of Mirafiori (October 2025)	Past	All	The artwork is placed in the target area and offers a good link to all NEB/cultural aspects of the interventions. Links > official opening events interview and details M. Nelson
Partners internal meeting (October 2025)	Past	Partners (Public, NGO)	
Miraforum (November 2025)	Past	All	A series of thematic round tables collecting inputs from citizens and interested parties to find development trajectories for the district. These inputs are useful to guide the co-creation process.
Co-creation of a map of the neighbourhood, led by ULAB and Fondazione Mirafiori (September 2025)	Past	All	The map highlights the “treasures” of Mirafiori and proposes thematic tours to discover its green infrastructure, cultural heritage and art and local stories. Link > social media post
Open call for the director of the landscape festival (October 2025)	Past	All	International open call Link> open call
Demolition and removal of abusive gardens (from October 2025)	Ongoing	All	Guided by the Municipality
Field trip with technical experts for challenges definition (January 2026)	Past	All	Technical site inspections to jointly analyse current challenges in the area and identify potential solutions to be presented to citizens for the co-design sessions
Workshop with local partners for co-creation of NBS (November 2025)	Past	All	Finding a common understanding of the concept of NbS and defining a series of potential interventions to be proposed for the co-design exercise with citizens and stakeholders.
First NbS co-creation session with citizens and selected stakeholders (15th January 2025)	Past	All	Selection of challenges through perceptions and experiences mapping. Identification of suitable NbS interventions to address them and discussion on

			potential NbS selected by local partners.
AR reconstruction of the urban farms from the Polytechnic of Turin	Ongoing	Researchers from PoliTO	<p>The research and creation of an AR model of the urban farms and activities that characterised Mirafiori in the past will be linked with the promotion of the rich cultural and natural heritage of the area, and showcased during the Festival.</p> <p>The activity is linked to the interest of the local inhabitants towards the history of the place, before its industrial time. A similar activity was developed in the past, with the reconstruction of the Mirafiori Castle and a thematic NbS where the castle was placed (proGIreg).</p> <p>Link: reconstruction of the Mirafiori Castle</p>
Youth engagement activities led by F,	Ongoing	Civil Society/Youth groups/students	
First NBS development and definition of the calendar of the landscape festival	Planned	All	After the artistic director will be selected, he/she will work on the festival programme and on the development of the artistic NbS, based on the inputs from the territory.
Cultural and historical heritage meeting with UNITRE (University of the Third Age)	Planned	All	
Other co-creation sessions with citizens and selected stakeholders	Planned	All	Other co-creation sessions will be planned for the other intervention areas that are part of the greening actions of ClimaGen (e.g. Parco Sangone, “green corridor” area and surroundings (Piazza Santi Apostoli), other artistic NbS).

Table 11 Overview of the Co-creation Activities in Turin

Trondheim, Norway

Short description of the area:

Trondheim lies on the south shore of Trondheim Fjord at the mouth of the River Nidelva. Trondheim's new municipal Plan for Natural Diversity will guide the municipality in becoming area-neutral, with zero net-loss of nature to stop the loss of natural diversity due to land changes. ClimaGen will contribute to this objective by developing co-created initiatives in the Områdesatsning (Area Based Development Programme, ABDP), a collaboration between the Norwegian State, the municipality and the local community that provides tools to facilitate the improvement of living conditions in an area that faces important challenges at all levels: infrastructure, economic, environmental, social etc. The programmes strengthen an area's own resources and mobilise inhabitants, private and public organisations in a common effort.

Short description of the objective for the area:

Trondheim is implementing an Area Based Development Programme (ABDP) in Lademoen, supported by an annual base budget of €400k and additional infrastructure funding. The Nyhavna district, a key part of this transformation, is a former harbour and brownfield area that includes 13 WWII heritage structures and is being redeveloped through co-created strategic planning. The Nyhavna Quality Programme envisions a flexible, resilient, and nature-based district with sustainable mobility and net-zero ambitions aligned with Trondheim's Mission City goals. Through ClimaGen, Trondheim will enhance green and blue infrastructures by 25%, linking Nyhavna to other Lademoen districts through biodiversity corridors and green mobility paths. The municipality will cluster small initiatives—like “Nature Leads the Way”—to connect social and cultural hubs, introduce pocket gardens, and replace lawns with meadows. Collaboration with other local organisations will support co-creation, sustainable design, and inclusive urban governance through the ClimaLab framework. Regenerative land use, urban gardening, and biodiversity restoration will address soil pollution and reuse vegetation displaced by construction. Cultural and artistic programmes, supported by KORO and local institutions, will strengthen community identity and engagement in Nyhavna's renewal. Overall, Trondheim's ClimaGen activities aim to integrate environmental regeneration, innovation, and inclusive participation into a long-term model for sustainable urban transformation.

Lessons and Challenges from Practice:

Challenges in co-creation activities: A key challenge stems from the area's significant social diversity. This heterogeneity makes it complex to design and implement co-creation solutions that achieve universal applicability and effectively serve all community groups' varied needs. When many people are collaborating, it also takes longer to complete a task or a project. At the same time, co-creation and wide distribution of ownership on proposals and solutions give strength to the project and potentially political support.

Reflections and lessons-learnt: A primary lesson is the critical need for municipal adaptability. Co-creation strategies must be flexible to accommodate the diverse and at times conflicting needs of the area's distinct communities. Establishing direct communication channels between citizens and local authorities, like community meetings, has proven to be an effective practice. Further significant learning relates to internal municipal processes. Achieving robust political anchoring and ensuring effective cross-sectoral collaboration for these co-creation initiatives remains a challenge.

Activity	Past – Ongoing – Planned	Target group(s) (Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society)	Additional comments/links
Trondheim's municipality Area Investment project for Lademoen-Nyhavna, started in 2022, is based on co-creation and participatory approaches.	Past	Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society	Site AIP https://www.trondheim.kommune.no/aktuelt/om-kommunen/annet/prosjekter-fra-a-a/omradesatsingene-i-trondheim/
Partners meet regularly in "Lademoen AIP forum" and "ClimaGen community of practice" with colleagues from other municipal departments and public stakeholders to exchange knowledge and coordinate our various projects, including the definition of ClimaGen baseline.	Ongoing	Public/Civil society	This cross-departmental collaboration is essential for giving our work a broader dimension and effectively engaging with stakeholders. In general, a participatory approach is maintained for all projects concerning parks and urban spaces.
Annual community meetings for the neighbourhood, initially managed by the municipality, are now organised by the stakeholders themselves and serve as a channel between the community and the authorities. (Lamosnakk og Lamotreff)	Past - Ongoing	Public	Dialogue, information, workshops, getting to know each other, and cultural experiences. The local organisations have now taken over the responsibility of organising these meetings.
A strategic plan for public spaces and connections was co-created with local stakeholders, including middle school students, organisations, and employees in municipal institutions. The plan also included input received through public meetings and other channels.	past	Public	The process started in 2024, finished in 2025.
Co-creation with students at Nyhavna area in close cooperation with the Municipality, Nyhavna development and the national railway company BaneNOR. Covers landscape analysis,	Ongoing and future	Students, public, private	Includes both registrations, analysis, building 1:1 and study of plants and vegetation. (Railwaypark, Ormen Langes veg, Talerøret, Nyhavna)

ecology, planning and architecture, biology			
Co-creation of an urban space with a neighbourhood: removal of regulated parking, conversion of lawn areas into perennial beds with the residents, and placement of benches and upgraded lighting.	Past - ongoing	Public/private	The project is developing and will be continued in 2026. The benches that were put out following co-creation activities to engage families and bring them closer to nature were also used by youth at night. The residents ask for more flowers and want to find a better solution for the benches.
Makeover and enlarging the park "Strandveiparken", based on dialogue with the local schools and neighbourhood.	Past	Public/Civil Society	Finished summer 2025, included cleaning of contaminated soil, new playground and reuse of furniture. Reuse of vegetation after cleaning the soil
Developing and sustaining urban agriculture e.g. with the local church, local school and local gardener association in Lademoen.	Past and future	Public, private	"Dyrkefestival Barnas katedral" "Lademoen dyrke- og hagelag hagedag" Lilleby school garden
Designjam with design students. How can green engage young people?	Ongoing	students	
Dugnad - taking care of nature in parks and green areas with the children in the schools nearby, including planting bulbs and removal of invasive species	Ongoing	Public - local schools	Organising a planting day in the park of Buran, engaging children of fourth grade from two local schools to plant flower bulbs to have early flowers for the bees and bumblebees in the spring, as well as to make the park more beautiful. Organising several days put in the green areas, removing invasive species together with goats.
Planning with Rosendal Theatre and the art Biennale of Trondheim, to find opportunities for cultural action	Ongoing - future	Public and civil society	

<p>We are analysing the use of public spaces targeted for increased green areas. This analysis is designed to survey public sentiment and determine their satisfaction with the situation as it is.</p>	<p>ongoing</p>	<p>Public and civil society</p>	
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Table 12 Overview of the Co-creation Activities in Trondheim

Replication cities

Cluj-Napoca, Romania

Short description of the area:

Cluj-Napoca is located in the northwestern part of Romania, a city that is surrounded by rural areas. In order to strengthen these interdependencies, Cluj-Napoca will implement pilot interventions focused on urban greening and nature-based solutions, along with local environmental compensation processes within the Cluj Rural–Urban Hub. These pilots will be designed for testing, learning, and later replication across the wider metropolitan area.

Short description of the objective for the area:

The selected ClimaGen Living Lab sites will be developed through planning and co-creation processes guided by ClimaGen’s principles and methodologies. The Hub is a collaborative, bottom-up initiative involving the municipalities of Cluj-Napoca, Ciurila, and Petreștii de Jos, along with the Cluj Metropolitan Area Association and the C-EDU Educational Cluster (CEDU). Its goal is to meet the needs of residents in both urban and nearby rural areas through sustainable co-design aligned with the EU’s Rural Action Plan. Projects will focus on improving coexistence and quality of life through shared activities, infrastructure, and innovation. Cluj-Napoca will build on experiences from the proGInreg and CO4CITIES projects, as well as its involvement in the Cities Mission and European Digital Innovation Hub, to implement digitally supported solutions. Between 2024 and 2027, the city will operate an innovation experiment fund and dashboard to track progress and inform ClimaGen’s Impact Model. CEDU will serve as a neutral platform for collaboration among municipalities, companies, NGOs, and universities. ClimaGen will also foster youth entrepreneurship focused on nature-based regeneration and social innovation through experimental funding and participatory design. Insights from this work will contribute to the Regional Innovation Valley and the New European Innovation Agenda. Through its cross-sector cooperation and education-driven model, Cluj-Napoca aims to position itself as a ClimaGen Living Lab pioneer, offering replicable structures for other cities.

Lessons and Challenges from Practice:

Challenges in co-creation activities: Despite the co-creation approach aiming for multi-level engagement for the achievement of a common vision, this is a complex process that requires time, long-term involvement and willingness from all stakeholders to be achieved.

Reflections and lessons-learned: The co-creation takes place in a real-life environment, which means that the political situation and other occasions that affect the community are directly influencing the activities of the Living Lab.

Activity	Past – Ongoing – Planned	Target group(s) (Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society)	Additional comments/links
Synergies with other projects in the city	Past	All	<p>The Municipality of Cluj-Napoca has already implemented several co-creation and participatory approaches in urban development. Since 2017, the city has run an online participatory budgeting process through which citizens can propose and vote for local projects. In parallel, Com'ON Cluj-Napoca, a participatory budgeting program dedicated to youth, has supported hundreds of community initiatives proposed and selected by young residents. Building on this culture of civic involvement, the city is now introducing FIX – the Innovation and Experiment Fund, a new mechanism that supports small-scale pilots and community-driven experiments, enabling residents, NGOs, and institutions to collaboratively test solutions in real-life settings. To strengthen structured dialogue, the City created the CIIC – Centre for Innovation and Civic Imagination, a permanent consultation and co-design platform used in drafting the Integrated Urban Development Strategy (SIDU 2021–2030) and in shaping flagship public space projects such as Parcul Est and the Someş riverside regeneration. Moreover, the city was partner in the CO4CITIES project, focused on co-creation and co-management of urban commons, and is now building on that experience through the 2Nite project (URBACT IV), where participatory methods are applied to urban safety and night-time economy. Through these mechanisms, citizen input has directly influenced both micro-initiatives and large-scale urban transformations, consolidating a culture of participatory governance at the local level.</p>
Address possible interventions in areas with elderly residents	Past	Civil society	
Started creating the Living Lab's initial	Present	All	

governmental structure			
Stakeholder mapping with the academic sector	Present	Research/City administrators	
Finalise the structure of the Living Lab and bring on board all relevant actors	Future	All	
Connect with FIX (Innovation & Experiment Fund)	Future	All	

Table 13 Overview of the Co-creation Activities in Cluj-Napoca

Eindhoven, The Netherlands

Short description of the area:

Eindhoven will focus its ClimaGen efforts on the Limbeek-Noord district, a mainly 1950s neighbourhood originally built by the Philips company to address housing shortages through innovative stacked housing and shared green spaces. Once a model of modern urban planning, the area now suffers from neglect, declining historical value, limited social cohesion and health issues. Despite ample green space, biodiversity and community engagement are low, and rising development pressure threatens both the area's greenery and affordability. Today, Limbeek-Noord is more a transient zone than a lifelong community.

Short description of the objective for the area:

Eindhoven is planning the redevelopment of the Limbeek-Noord district and expects ClimaGen to help design greener, more inclusive public spaces that foster community and support climate goals. The city's focus will be on resident engagement, community building, and integrating public spaces that promote climate neutrality, adaptation, and health. In line with its commitment as a Climate-neutrality Mission City to become climate-neutral by 2030, Eindhoven places climate action at the heart of all urban redevelopment projects. ClimaGen will be used to refine regeneration plans in Limbeek-Noord through nature-based solutions. Building on its leadership in the UNaLAB project, the city will apply lessons learned to involve residents meaningfully in planning processes. In the current redevelopment schedule, housing initiatives are combined with green space development. ClimaGen will provide valuable insights for an even better future implementation of climate adaptation goals in area developments. Eindhoven also aims to exchange knowledge with other ClimaGen cities to strengthen its approach. The district's proximity to several Brainport campuses and ClimaGen's connection to excellent education institutes offer potential for green entrepreneurship and innovation. Initiatives such as Green Business Development and Green Infrastructure projects will link environmental sustainability with economic growth. Through these actions, Eindhoven will serve as a trailblazer and model for sustainable urban transformation within the ClimaGen network.

Lessons and Challenges from Practice:

Challenges in co-creation activities: In co-creation practices that involve multiple stakeholders, and especially residents or residents' organisations, a vision might be hard to explain. Providing concrete examples or other formats that allow people to visualise the solutions is essential and challenging.

Reflections and lessons-learned: It is important to combine challenges coming from different partners on a concrete and practical level. The creation of collaborations is vital for the co-creation to move forward.

Activity	Past – Ongoing – Planned	Target group(s) (Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society)
In Eindhoven, an extended participation in policy and projects has been implemented. In the Netherlands, every spatial initiative (from policy making to concrete building plans) is required to follow a participatory approach. In Eindhoven, the municipality has implemented co-creation on a lot of sites and projects,	Ongoing	
Pact Woensel-Zuid for streamlining challenges of different fields or research/work	Past	All
Locality workshop on defining challenges in the area and opportunities for cooperation	Past	Partners
Limbeek coalition meetings for discussions around the re-development of existing social housing, turning around the negative circle of socio-economic dynamics and linking the physical and social goals after defining them.	Ongoing	Civil Society
Kick-off meeting: brought together stakeholders for an initial moment to get to know each other, making an actor map, discussing important issues to tackle and linking the actors to the work packages.	Past	
Understand and strengthen youth engagement and arts & culture	Future	Civil Society

Table 14 Overview of the Co-creation Activities in Eindhoven

Gernika, Spain

Short description of the area:

Gernika-Lumo is a town in Spain's Basque Country, located within the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve. This reserve, declared a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve in 1984, spans more than 22,000 hectares of diverse ecosystems, including coasts, wetlands, forests, and mountains. Urdaibai is especially valuable for its biodiversity, hosting over 200 bird species and numerous rare or endangered plants and animals. However, climate change poses serious threats to the region's natural balance. Rising sea levels endanger about half of the Urdaibai marshes, while floods and the loss of sandbanks are expected in the coming years. In response, the region has implemented a coastal protection plan to mitigate these impacts. The Gernika-Lumo City Council has also carried out an energy diagnosis and a greenhouse gas emissions inventory to identify key areas for reducing emissions, particularly from municipal buildings and public lighting. Building on insights from the H2020 ProLight project, the city integrates socio-economic, environmental, and cultural perspectives in alignment with the New European Bauhaus principles.

Short description of the objective for the area:

Through the ClimaGen initiative, Gernika aims to engage residents in creative and participatory processes that connect sustainability, art, and innovation. Local organisations such as GERN, GAIA, and ESK will help foster artistic and entrepreneurial projects to design and manage health-promoting, climate-resilient green spaces. Gernika will engage its cultural and creative industries in designing new healthy green spaces and assessing how these spaces enhance residents' well-being. The city's approach combines two main goals: creating health-oriented green spaces and integrating art into these environments to improve quality of life. Work will take place in the residential neighbourhood of Renteria and previously industrial areas which includes redeveloping the old Dalia factory into a space for residences and meetings, connected by natural landscapes and cycle paths for an inclusive experience. Through ClimaGen, Gernika will establish a Living Lab to address territorial challenges, promote Urdaibai's natural assets, and strengthen regional competitiveness through open innovation. The lab will operate on a regional strategy with an international outlook, focusing on ecosystem protection, biodiversity enhancement, cultural well-being, and green economy development. It will link local companies with sustainability and innovation strategies, support creative entrepreneurship, and foster talent rooted in the territory. Residents will participate actively in co-creation and awareness initiatives coordinated by municipal staff and community associations. Gernika's actions align with the city's Urban Agenda and long-standing collaboration with citizens on sustainability projects. As a member of the Basque sustainability network Udalsarea 21, Gernika will share best practices, attract partnerships and funding, and lead regional cooperation to replicate successful renaturing projects across other cities.

Lessons and Challenges from Practice:

Challenges in co-creation activities: The ClimaGen Living Lab is a difficult task. There are new stakeholders coming in as the team continues to work on its ClimaGen activities, which weren't considered before. While this is positive, their type of engagement, frequency, and contribution should be clearly defined from the initial stages of implementation.

Reflections and lessons-learned: Various new stakeholders are showing interest in ClimaGen and could be involved further in the ClimaGen Living Lab's activities. The initial list of stakeholders wasn't exhaustive, and the team is ready to listen to others, understand new interests and bring more organisations in.

Activity	Past – Ongoing – Planned	Target group(s) (Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society)	Additional comments/links
The team has extensive knowledge through previous projects such as Prolight, and other activities.	Past		
Natural regeneration plan	Past	All	
Urban Clima plan focusing on mobility, biodiversity and NBSs	Past	All	
Participation process co-design	Present	All	The neighbourhood must be involved from the very beginning.
Co-design start-up initiatives	Present	All	Real expertise and examples for start-ups are needed.
Plan of co-creation activities	Present	All	Identification of actions.
A chat vision of the future is planned	Future	All	

Table 15 Overview of the Co-creation Activities in Gernika

Thessaloniki, Greece

Short description of the area:

Thessaloniki is a historical city, founded in 315 BC, and is the second largest city in Greece. The city has evolved over centuries, both employing expansion as well as developing new layers of the city on top of older ones. The present structure of what used to be the 'historic part' of the city was mainly formed after an enormous fire burned a great part of the city in 1917. The greatest part of the city, after two world wars, which caused a large wave of emigration, resulted in a highly densely built environment with limited green spaces. Almost a decade ago the city's seafront went through deep renovation, providing a large area of walking paths, parks, recreation areas, and gathering points, where many people enjoy each day. Nevertheless, the interior of the city has remained unaffected by this renovation, with an absence of adequate 'canyons' to let the city breathe, and very limited public spaces especially at the neighbourhood level. Today's discussion to further extend the successful seafront renovation to nearby municipalities is gaining significant attention, since the core of the city remains unprepared to mitigate climate change, improve social bonding at the local, and neighbourhood level, upgrade microclimatic conditions and well-being within the city.

Short description of the objective for the area:

Thessaloniki will apply ClimaGen methodologies in the Fix – Giannitson – Railway Station district on the city's western side. In its eastern part, the area includes the Port of Thessaloniki and the Railway Station and is undergoing major transformations. It contains historic industrial complexes, including the Fix Brewery and the Mylos flour mill, alongside high-value private investments. Public projects are also planned, such as a Holocaust Museum and a Metropolitan Park on abandoned land. The urban fabric is currently fragmented, with vacant buildings and unmanaged green spaces that could become urban lungs if ownership barriers are addressed. Land uses include offices, malls, hotels, recreational areas, and residential enclaves, some of which are low-income and increasingly pressured by gentrification. Through its ClimaGen Living Lab, Thessaloniki will test participatory planning for a fair transition, focusing on nature-based solutions to improve microclimates, citizen participation, and social cohesion. The city's resilience strategy emphasises restoring its relationship with the sea and implementing climate-neutral action plans as part of the Mission Cities initiative. Local partners MDAT and AUTH will manage ClimaGen activities, combining municipal strategy implementation with scientific and engineering support. Stakeholders from public, private, and civil society sectors, as well as resident associations, will be involved in co-creation to enhance nature-based urban qualities while mitigating gentrification and ensuring replicable methods for future projects.

Lessons and Challenges from Practice:

Challenges in co-creation activities: Currently, the Living Lab is a complex initiative since it requires significant involvement by various stakeholders at many different levels, which is challenging for Thessaloniki's ecosystem. This might also risk lacking identity and a healthy structure that can ensure the sustainability of the outcomes long-term and beyond the project. Moreover, fragmentation of the population is a potential challenge given the current political situation and cultural differences.

Reflections and lessons learned: The Thessaloniki pilot area is extensive and highly diverse, involving a broad and heterogeneous range of stakeholders. The co-creation approach should therefore engage smaller, targeted groups individually to ensure more focused, context-specific, and actionable contributions. In addition, face-to-face discussions with key stakeholders holding

significant influence are essential to secure alignment, address early constraints, and strengthen commitment.

Activity	Past – Ongoing – Planned	Target group(s) (Public / Private / Academia / Civil Society)	Additional comments/links
The Major Development Agency Thessaloniki, in close collaboration with the Municipality of Thessaloniki and other municipalities of the wider metropolitan area, has already implemented a wide range of co-creation and participatory approaches in various urban projects outside of the ClimaGen project.	Past / ongoing	Authorised / public groups / private / academia / civil society initiations / multiethnic communities	<p>These initiatives have been developed through systematic and inclusive processes that bring together a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including local authorities, community groups, NGOs, academic institutions, private sector representatives, and residents.</p> <p>Some of the main areas where co-creation has played a central role are in the implementation of greening projects, regeneration projects, affordable housing initiatives, climate mitigation and adaptation actions, etc.</p>
Experience method stakeholder mapping	Past	All	Systematically identify and categorize actors based on their influence, interests, capacities, and lived experience related to the project area, ensuring both institutional stakeholders and community voices are meaningfully represented
Engagement strategy and participatory process roadmap	Past / present	All	A structured stakeholder engagement strategy and roadmap to establish the Thessaloniki ClimaLab, ensuring the active involvement of local authorities, businesses, civil society, academia, and communities through co-creation workshops.
Capacity development among all stakeholder	Past	Partners	Dependency upon all stakeholders and the municipality for stakeholder development
One-by-one discussions with main stakeholders with strong influence	Present/Future	All	Main stakeholders with strong influence over the area's transformation include the Municipality, the Regional Unit Authority (Metropolitan Thessaloniki), private real estate investors, major landowners

			(such as Hellenic Train Company), and the Hellenic Ministry of Culture due to the presence of listed industrial heritage buildings. One-to-one discussions with these actors are critical for trust building, clarifying expectations, and creating the conditions for strategic partnerships and long-term commitment to the Thessaloniki ClimaLab
Panels with different communities	Present/Future	All	
Define conflicts and alliances	Present/Future	All	
Continuous work with the municipality	Present/Future	City administrators	
Create a common vision across the whole ecosystem	Future	All	

Table 16 Overview of the Co-creation Activities in Thessaloniki

The Consortium

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ClimaGen – Climate-resilient reGeneration and renaturing for, by and with vulnerable neighbourhoods, striving towards net-zero. climagen.eu